

CHILD RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D1.3 – ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I

Workpackage: WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology
Definition

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of ChildRescue WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition and specifically, it represents the work conducted for “T1.3 - ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for Missing Children Investigation”.

The aim of this deliverable, according to the DoA, is to describe the ChildRescue integrated missing children investigation cycle methodology.

To achieve this, and further to the description provided to the DoA, this deliverable picks up the work done in “T1.1 - Identification of Stakeholders' Needs and User Requirements” and “D1.1 – User Requirements” in particular, together with the considerations made in “T1.2-Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues” and the Ethics Advisory Board suggestions, to refine, augment and systematically apply the findings from the User Requirements to analytically and visually describe the processes by which both pilot cases (Missing Children Investigation and Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Migrant Minors) can be merged on the same overall process of ChildRescue.

In order to do so, a comprehensive landscape analysis has been performed on the main, already identified, domains of interest and currently used related technologies, as well as the first steps towards innovative research that has been decided that may become of use in later stages of the project.

The first domain of interest that has been identified is “Business Process Re-Engineering and Change Management”, where the methods of applying new processes to existing workflows can drive change without creating obstructions to current operations are investigated. This is deemed necessary for minimising resistance to change when the integration of ChildRescue is attempted on existing processes.

The second domain is that of Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness, where the current trends and state-of-the art of approaches close to that of ChildRescue are investigated.

The third domain is Behavioural and Activity Profiling Theories, which has been described to provide a basis for the work that is being done for “WP2 - Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation” and specifically “T2.1-Behavioural and Activity Profiling of Missing Children”.

After that, the project’s main methodology is being described, starting with the mapping of the stakeholders and their relations in a way that eases the integration of everyone involved with the processes of ChildRescue. Then, following the four steps of the investigation cycle, the workflows and dataflows of the various processes are mapped and described.

Finally, a new research proposition is made, that of calculating a critical mass of social sensors depending on each area for the effectiveness of the mobile notifications, namely the investigation of a method to prioritise how many mobile users that have ChildRescue installed on their devices are required to maximise the effectiveness of the alerts, based on population and building density, the transportation map, and the morphology of the terrain. It has been verified that no similar research has been carried out, so the extend, the scope and the ways of using the results will be decided at a later stage.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Purpose & Scope	8
1.2	Structure of the deliverable	9
1.3	Relation to other WPs & Tasks	10
2	Landscape Analysis	11
2.1	ChildRescue Domains of Interest	11
2.1.1	Categorisation of Domains of Interest	11
2.1.2	Business Process Re-engineering – Change Management	12
2.1.2.1	<i>Change management</i>	12
2.1.2.2	<i>Business Process Management and Reengineering</i>	14
2.1.3	Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness	19
2.1.3.1	<i>Crowdsourcing</i>	19
2.1.3.2	<i>Social Innovation</i>	23
2.1.3.3	<i>Collective Awareness</i>	27
2.1.4	Behavioural and Activity Profiling Theories and Research Review	30
2.2	ChildRescue-relevant Technologies and Systems	35
2.2.1	Technologies and Systems for Missing People Identification	35
2.2.2	Technologies and Systems for Refugee Management	44
2.3	Conclusions & Key Take-aways	48
3	ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for the Missing Children Investigation Cycle	49
3.1	Stakeholders' Mapping	49
3.2	Methodology Definition	50
3.2.1	Preparation and Profiling	53
3.2.1.1	<i>Scope</i>	53
3.2.1.2	<i>Workflow</i>	53
3.2.1.3	<i>Dataflow</i>	58
3.2.2	Coordination and Collaboration	60
3.2.2.1	<i>Scope</i>	60
3.2.2.2	<i>Workflow</i>	60
3.2.2.3	<i>Dataflow</i>	65
3.2.3	Action	65
3.2.3.1	<i>Scope</i>	65
3.2.3.2	<i>Workflow</i>	66
3.2.3.3	<i>Dataflow</i>	70

3.2.4 Archiving 70

 3.2.4.1 Scope..... 70

 3.2.4.2 Workflow..... 71

 3.2.4.3 Dataflow..... 74

3.3 Plan for the Adoption of the Methodology: Social Sensors Critical Mass ... 75

4 Conclusions & Next Steps 79

5 Annex I: References 80

List of Figures

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WP/tasks	10
Figure 2-1 Structure and Categorisation of ChildRescue Domains of Interest	12
Figure 2-2 BPM lifecycle, retrieved from [9]	16
Figure 2-3 BPM core elements, success factors and challenges, retrieved from [12]	17
Figure 2-4 Workflow Chart WP 2.1	34
Figure 3-1 ChildRescue Stakeholders & Actors	50
Figure 3-2 Preparation and Profiling workflow	57
Figure 3-3 Preparation and Profiling dataflow	59
Figure 3-4 Coordination and Collaboration workflow	64
Figure 3-5 Coordination and Collaboration dataflow	65
Figure 3-6 Action workflow	69
Figure 3-7 Action dataflow	70
Figure 3-8 Archiving workflow	73
Figure 3-9 Archiving dataflow	74

List of Tables

Table 2-1 Crowdsourcing literature definitions	20
Table 2-2 Social innovation literature definitions	24
Table 2-3 Digital social innovation literature definitions	25
Table 2-4 Definitions relevant with the term Collective Awareness	28
Table 2-5 Different Categories of analysis and corresponding algorithms [60]	32
Table 2-6 Different types of missing children cases and appropriate theories	33
Table 3-1 Actors	51
Table 3-2 Preparation and profiling workflow steps	53
Table 3-3 Coordination and Collaboration workflow steps	61
Table 3-4 Action workflow steps	67
Table 3-5 Archiving workflow steps	71

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

ChildRescue is guided by the vision to reduce the primary time between the moment a child is reported missing and the time when it is found while empowering citizens to act as social sensors, by developing an integrated methodology that will transform the way missing children investigations are currently held. ChildRescue recognises two distinct cases that are considered under a common approach; that of handling a missing child emergency and that of discovering and identifying an unaccompanied migrant minor.

With that vision at its centre, the present deliverable, D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I", aims at defining a solid methodology for engaging an as broad as possible citizens pool in a missing child case and offering a unique solution for cross-stakeholder collaboration and identification of missing and unaccompanied minors. The methodology should capture all prominent and underlying interactions among stakeholders and the system as well as the data exchange among them.

To accomplish that goal, a state of the art analysis of certain ChildRescue domains of interest, that could be of help for the development of the Integrated Methodology, precedes the methodology, while the methodology is analysed in the four Missing Child Investigation Cycle stages that have been already recognized from the proposal basis and workflows and dataflows are specified for each of them.

In particular, the scope of this deliverable is:

- To organise and study the research topics of interest to ChildRescue with respect to a categorisation (taxonomy-like) of the ChildRescue-related research areas;
- To extensively review existing approaches/methodologies/platforms/tools along multiple dimensions with respect to the ChildRescue context;
- To investigate in-depth the existing technologies and systems for missing people identification and refugee management;
- To map ChildRescue stakeholders in a way that all interactions among them will be distinguishable;
- To elaborate on a holistic ChildRescue Missing Children Investigation Cycle Methodology that will re-engineer the existing business processes of the organisations operating in the missing children or unaccompanied migrant minors domains, without disrupting their current processes;
- To take the approval of the ChildRescue EAB with respect to the predictive algorithms that will be developed in the course of the project, providing a detailed description of the data these algorithms will use and the assumptions they will make, in order to ensure compliance with the Ethics Requirement 10 from the Ares(2017)4601286 Ethics Summary;
- To prepare an initial plan for the adoption of the methodology, identifying what would be a critical social sensors mass for the success of the ChildRescue system and respective vision.

D1.3 constitutes the first iteration of the ChildRescue Integrated Missing Children Investigation Cycle Methodology. It is released within the context of Work Package 1 "ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition" and reports the work implemented under Task 1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for Missing Children Investigation". D1.3 will be refined and finalised in a second iteration, reported in D1.4, close to the end of the second year of the ChildRescue project implementation (M21).

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The rest of the document at hand is structured as follows:

- Section 2 exposes the ChildRescue Landscape Analysis for the identified domains of interest, starting from Business Process Management point of reference, so that methods and solutions that could change business processing without being intrusive can be identified, and proceeding with Crowdsourcing and Collective Awareness techniques and Behavioural and Activity Profiling theories, to explore ways to engage people and leverage behavioural and activity information to predict and come up with decisions. Technologies and systems that are currently in use both for missing people identification (Section 2.2.1), as well as for refugee management (Section 2.2.2) are also analysed and reported.
- Section 3 then describes the ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for the Missing Children Investigation Cycle implementing a stakeholder mapping where the relations between ChildRescue actors are analysed in detail. Here lies the core of the specific deliverable, which is the definition of the ChildRescue methodology, where the suggested processes are presented. The scope, the workflow and the dataflow for each of the 4 stages of a missing child investigation cycle, as already identified in the DoA and also presented in D1.1, are described, not as part of a sequential process, but in a way that every stage is autonomous and can run in parallel and/or independently with the other processes. Lastly, a plan for the adoption of the methodology is explored, based on the "social sensors critical mass" that is needed to use ChildRescue solution, in order for it to be considered successful.
- Section 4 summarises the work performed and documented in this deliverable and provides directions and recommendations for the next steps of the project implementation.
- Annex I lists the references included in the present deliverable.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I" reports, as already mentioned, the work implemented until M6 of the project duration in Task 1.3 for the elaboration of the integrated methodology. D1.3 takes input from D1.2 "Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues" and most importantly from D1.1 "User Requirements" to understand what is needed, what are the current problems and limitations that impede progress of Missing Children Investigation processes, which are the data protection, privacy and ethical issues that should be respected, and elaborate on the Integrated Missing Children Investigation Cycle Methodology accordingly.

On the other hand, D1.3 plays an instrumental role in ChildRescue since it aspires to be a "guide" for the work to be conducted during the project duration and therefore influences all other WPs and Tasks. However, the connection is more intense with WP2 "Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation" and WP3 "ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation" that will be based on the elaborated methodology to define in deeper analysis the scientific and technical background and develop the ChildRescue solution with respect to the Integrated Methodology reported in this deliverable.

The ChildRescue integrated methodology will be updated on M21 and reported in "D1.4 - ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release II", which will revise and finalise the ChildRescue integrated missing children investigation cycle methodology, as well as the requirements, considering the ChildRescue project advancements.

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WP/tasks

2 Landscape Analysis

2.1 ChildRescue Domains of Interest

2.1.1 Categorisation of Domains of Interest

In order to thoroughly study the state-of-play on the domains that would be of direct interest to ChildRescue, an identification and categorisation of these domains of interest was necessary.

The reasoning behind the choice of the domains to be bibliographically analysed was to acknowledge the scientific areas that are associated with ChildRescue from which useful conclusions can be drawn regarding the current state-of-the-art in these areas and the ways specific breakthroughs of these areas could be leveraged in the ChildRescue methodology and the respective solution.

In that view, such categorisation is split into three research areas, starting from the more high-level but core area of "Business Process Management" and continuing to more specific and complementary areas for the ChildRescue interests, that of "Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness" and "Behavioural and Activity Profiling".

While these 3 areas might seem independent and detached at a first glance, they "bind" together harmoniously under the ChildRescue concept. In particular, "Business Process Re-engineering – Change Management" serves as a cornerstone area as it encapsulates ChildRescue's vision, i.e. to define new processes, methods, techniques and means for the investigation of missing children that will complement the current systems and processes of the engaged organisations and gradually – and certainly not intrusively – substitute and relieve their present predicaments. ChildRescue perceives that its assets to achieve the desirable re-engineering step upon crowdsourcing and collective intelligence on the one hand and innovative profiling on the other hand, using data sources not considered before, such as social media data and combining them for the prediction of the most probable locations of the missing child. Therefore, "Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Intelligence" area, analysed in section 2.1.3, will serve as a source of new or not sufficiently exploited input in the investigation process of missing children, being in other words an "enabler" in the ChildRescue value proposition. Finally, "Behavioural and Activity Profiling" aims to be explored as an area that will provide added value to ChildRescue, leveraging all the gathered information and data regarding a missing child case, including information provided by citizens through crowdsourcing techniques, to form a profile for the missing child. The insights that will arise from this profiling along with information regarding the location of a missing child provided through crowdsourcing means, will support prediction with a better accuracy of all his/her possible locations.

The above presented structure and categorisation of the ChildRescue scientific areas that are considered as domains of interest and will be analysed bibliographically is also illustrated in Figure 2-1, below.

Figure 2-1 Structure and Categorisation of ChildRescue Domains of Interest

2.1.2 Business Process Re-engineering – Change Management

2.1.2.1 *Change management*

Introduction to change management

Organisational change is a field of management theory examining the stages that organisations go through as they progress [1] and it is a tool widely used to define the most appropriate strategy depending on the stage of the change organisations are currently at. Change management is a subdiscipline of organisational change and according to the Innovation and Organizational Change management Institute (IOCMI)¹ it is the people side of change. The people or human side of change management can be described as the alignment of the organisation's culture, values, people and behaviour [2]. According to [3] change management can also be defined as "the process of continually renewing an organization's direction, structure, and capabilities to serve the ever-changing needs of external and internal customers.

From the early 90s, Academia's attention has been focused on organisational change and change management. In this section an overview of change management will be presented, along with some theories and models that have been developed, in order to grasp the main issues that need to be

¹ <https://www.iocmi.org>

tended when employing change management. Also, the process followed when implementing change management will be briefly given along with some challenges associated with it.

As mentioned above, the attention in academia has been shifted towards organizational management especially after the 80s that labor mobility, market transparency, global capital flows and international communication has changed the scenery for the companies [2]. According to [4] companies only needed to utilise their resources in a way that was profitable when operating in a relative stable environment, but change management emerged in the moment companies started to face competitive environments that changed profoundly and in a high pace.

Managing change successfully

The constant changes and the adaptation of companies and organisations to those changes have boosted the development of change management theories, frameworks and models that can be of aid when employing change management. As in [5] review, change management can be analysed from different perspectives. They reviewed the existing literature from four different aspects, namely: the internal and external environment perspective (contextual issues), the substance of contemporary organisational changes point of view (content issues), the actions taken while the organisation undergoes the change angle (process issues), and the outcomes of the change aspect (criterion issues). Regarding the external or internal factors, they found out that change may be mainly imposed by two factors. The first factor is regulatory changes and the second one may emerge by the technological advancements that the competitors adopt and implement. The models that focus on content factors, such as organisation structure and strategic orientation, define the mission and direction of the organisation and are the basis of a long-term success. They are suitable for the conduct of organisational diagnosis, and for planning the potential impact of the change. Depending on the behavioural aspects of the participants the content factors can be combined in different ways in order to achieve the desirable result. Concerning the process issues related studies, that analyse the ongoing actions while the organisation undergoes the change, it was found out that the change occurs in multiple steps, that require time to develop and any attempt to reduce the time of these efforts seldom yields a satisfactory result. What is more, any mistakes may hinder or even stop the process. Finally, as far as the criterion issues are concerned, the reactions to organisational changes can be assessed by a variety of methods, including computer-based analysis or observation. What also can be taken into consideration in the assessment of the reaction to the change is, apart from the traditional criteria that measure effectiveness (e.g. job satisfaction), the evaluation of less used criteria (e.g. depression). Also, the frequent communication of results or milestones can assist the members to cope with the change.

Challenges and risks

In this section, some of the challenges when implementing change management are going to be presented. From a business perspective, booz&co. in the relevant report that they issued in 2004² conclude that there are some issues that need to be closely monitored when implementing change management. These are briefly described below. Initially the "human side" of the organisation needs to be addressed systematically, meaning that when change management is employed the as-is situation

² <https://www.devex.com/organizations/booz-co-49791>

is altered and that can lead to confusion and resistance. A way to deal with that phenomenon is to address each of the cases that may emerge separately and proactively. Another issue to be kept in mind is that the change must start at the top and involve every layer, with constant communication and with the channels of communication being open. What is more, an assessment of the cultural landscape and its potential reaction to change should be assessed before employing change management.

From an academia point of view, [6] after reviewing the existing literature came up with some steps that need to be followed if change management is to be successful. They assess that as a first step the idea or the innovation that calls for the change of the as-is situation and its context needs to be clearly defined, closely followed by a clear definition of the roles and the processes that need to be changed. What is more, the climate of change needs to be assessed, meaning that there needs to be a deep understanding of how the organisation operates in the current environment. A clear plan also needs to be crafted, including specific goals and clearly defined responsibilities. The leadership needs to be a pioneer when it comes to embracing the change plan. The importance of constant communication among all the layers in the organisation is explicitly mentioned by the researchers. Finally, attention is also given to incorporating any lessons learnt that may emerge while change management is employed.

It can be observed that from both a business perspective and an academia perspective, the issues that need to be given attention while implementing change management remain similar. Extra attention is given to the assessment of the current culture of the organisation, the involvement of all the people that work in it, the constant communication between the leadership and the rest of the employees and taking into consideration the lessons learnt while the process is ongoing.

Within the concept of ChildRescue, attention needs to be given to change management. As it is mentioned and explained throughout this and previous deliverables, ChildRescue aims at being a non-intrusive driver of change. That means that the processes currently followed by the missing children response organisations will slightly alter, if these organisations decide to incorporate the platform and app in the search of missing children. Even though the change is not going to be intrusive, some readjustment is going to take place. All the aforementioned challenges and risks need to be taken into consideration. Particularly, the communication among all the members of the organisations and the engagement to the change from the top to the bottom.

2.1.2.2 *Business Process Management and Reengineering*

Today's highly competitive environment has made it impossible for organisations to stay static³. A lot of attention has been given from both the academia and the business world on techniques, theories or models that could facilitate the constant changes. Two concepts that are widely but differently used in terms of their application are Business Process Management and Business Process Reengineering. The two concepts are often considered similar; however, they are different. In this section, an overview of the two concepts from mainly an academic point of view is going to be presented and the relevant literature, the architectures, key success factors and how both concepts but mainly Business Process Management applies to ChildRescue are going to be analysed.

³ <https://www.devex.com/organizations/booz-co-49791>

The notion of the term "process"

Process in the management science related literature mainly refers to the approach that converts inputs into outputs [7]. According to [7] a process is: "the manner in which the resources of an organisation are used in a reliable, repeatable and consistent way", in order for the organisation to achieve its goals. [8] defines business process as: "a complete, dynamically coordinated set of activities or logically related tasks that must be performed to deliver value to customers or to fulfil other strategic goals". [9] defines process as: "a collection of inter-related events, activities and decision points that involve a number of actors and objects, and that collectively lead to an outcome that is of value to at least one customer". Essentially, according to Bulletpoint (1996) there are four key features to any process, namely these are: predictable and definable inputs, a linear, logical sequence or flow, a set of clearly definable tasks or activities, and a predictable and desired outcome or result.

In the existing literature about Business Process Management, a lot of attention has been given to processes [10]. One of the issues that academia has tried to define is what constitutes a "better process". Mainly a better process includes the processes that contribute in an optimal way to meet the strategic objectives of an organisation [10]. BPM is employed when the level of contribution is not met or when the set key performance indicators (KPIs) are also not met. BPM is mainly utilised so that the performance of the organisation can be enhanced. BPM can be associated with the KPIs and can be a means to meet them by terms of employing the appropriate and necessary tools that can be of assistance in the analysis of what hinders and stalls meeting the KPIs. According to [10], one way to mine data in order to analyse them and extract information is the employment of statistical tools that can measure the variability of the processes. Another way [10] can be the employment of operations research, in order to find an optimal solution for complex issues with a lot of constraints and options. [11] mention that Information Technology (IT) can also be employed to manage business processes, as more and more processes that were previously hand-filled in paper form are replaced by their electronic counterparts, giving rise to BPM. In the following section definitions of BPM as they were found in the literature are presented, along with some key factors that need to be fulfilled when employing BPM and some challenges that need to be overcome.

Business Process Management

In this section Business Process Management (BPM) is explained along with its key success factors and challenges. Some definitions of BPM as they were found in the literature are given.

As [7] states the existing literature on modern management techniques such as business process re-engineering, benchmarking or business process management is plentiful. The concept of BPM has been defined in various ways some of them are described below. [7] states that: "BPM is a structured approach to analyse and continually improve fundamental activities such as manufacturing, marketing, communications and other major elements of a company's operation". [9] claims that: "BPM is the art and science of overseeing how work is performed in an organisation to ensure consistent outcomes and to take advantage of improvement opportunities". They also claim that BPM does not have to do with micromanagement, as in overseeing that every single task in an organisation is performed efficiently, but rather has to do with ensuring that the overall processes that add value to the organization and its customers are performed efficiently. What is more, they mention that: "BPM has a body of methods, techniques and tools to discover, analyse, redesign, execute and monitor business processes." The above definition is what links BPM to business processes.

In the Figure 2-2 below, the BPM lifecycle is graphically explained. Mainly BPM as a continuous cycle that includes the process of identification, where the problem is posed, the process discovery, where the relevant processes are documented, the process analysis, where the as-is situation is identified, the process re-design, where the existing processes are improved, the process implementation, where the improvements are implemented, and the process monitoring and controlling, where the new processes are evaluated and feedback is provided.

Figure 2-2 BPM lifecycle, retrieved from [9]

Strategic Alignment	Governance	Methods	Information Technology	People	Culture	Factors
Process Improvement Planning	Process Management Decision Making	Process Design & Modelling	Process Design & Modelling	Process Skills & Expertise	Responsiveness of Process Change	Capability Areas
Strategy & Process Capability Linkage	Process Roles & Responsibilities	Process Implementation & Execution	Process Implementation & Execution	Process Management Knowledge	Process Values & Beliefs	
Enterprise Process Architecture	Process Metrics & Performance Linkage	Process Monitoring & Control	Process Monitoring & Control	Process Education	Process Attitudes and Behaviours	
Process Measures	Process Related Standards	Process Improvement & Innovation	Process Improvement & Innovation	Process Collaboration	Leadership Attention to Process	
Process Customers & Stakeholders	Process management Compliance	Process Program & Project Management	Process Program & Project Management	Process Management Leaders	Process Management Social Networks	

Figure 2-3 BPM core elements, success factors and challenges, retrieved from [12]

J. vom Brocke and M. Rosemann [12], after an exhaustive review of the relevant literature, concluded that the success factors that need to be kept in mind when employing BPM, can fall under six categories as depicted in the table above. Particularly, BPM needs to be aligned with the overall strategy of the organisation and the strategic alignment factor refers to linking the priorities of the organisation with the followed processes. The governance factor refers to establishing different roles and responsibilities in all the levels of BPM. Methods with regards to BPM are the tools and techniques employed along any BPM activities. Information technology is of extreme importance when it comes to BPM, especially with reference to process analysis, modelling and support. Special attention has been given to software with an understanding of the processes that need to be followed when BPM is to be employed. People are the ones that apply the processes or get affected by them. This factor is the reflection of BPM to the human capital. Culture stands for the collective values that govern an organisation and BPM studies indicate that culture is a very important factor when it comes to the people accepting the new processes imposed by BPM. The above six factors came up after a compilation of a variety of studies that looked at BPM through different aspects, some of them were more technical in nature, some more business oriented, and others more conceptual or behavioural.

One of the key components of BPM is that it is not intrusive as it does not radically change processes but only improves the existing ones, thus it is the one that will be followed in ChildRescue. Even though

BPM is non-intrusive, there are still challenges that need to be addressed when employing it. Mainly that the above six factors of success also hinder risks if not given proper attention. If BPM is not aligned with the strategy of the organisation, the new processes will not only not help but may even hinder the whole course of action and mission. As for the governance, the roles need to be separate and clear, or else the efficiency will be hindered. Regarding the methods and information technology, the appropriate processes and the right tools need to be employed. In this case, the appropriate needs and tools to be assessed refers to how suitable these needs and tools are. The people are of extreme importance when BPM is employed, as the human capital needs to be informed at every step of the way about the new processes thus making communication in all the levels of hierarchy of extreme importance. The culture is also an important factor as it needs to be responsive to change and processes need to be an integral part of the change. The leadership needs to be engaged when BPM is employed and needs to be in constant communication with the rest of the members of the organisation.

Business Process Reengineering

In this section an overview of Business Process Reengineering (BPR) is provided. BPR originated after the 1980s, when organisations were in need of fundamental changes in order to create and maintain a sustainable competitive advantage, by radically improving the existing processes [13]. [13], who reviewed the up to that point literature presented an overview of BPR and some definitions were also given. Some of the definitions are provided below.

According to [14] BPR is: "the analysis and design of work flows and processes within and between organisations". [15] claim BPR is: "the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes to achieve dramatic improvements in critical, contemporary measures of performance, such as cost, quality, service, and speed.". [16] with a focus on rethinking defines BPR as: "the rethinking, restructuring and streamlining of the business structure, processes, methods of working, management systems and external relationships through which value is created and delivered". [17] state that BPR: "involves the concurrent redesign of processes, organisations, and their supporting information systems to achieve radical improvement in time, cost, quality, and customers' regard for the company's products and services". [18] describes BPR as: "the fundamental rethinking and redesign of operating processes and organisational structure, the focus is on the organisation's core competencies, to achieve dramatic improvements in organisational performance, as BPR's essential components".

BPM, BPR and ChildRescue

BPR is used when the as-is processes are going to be radically and fundamentally changed, by changing the whole strategy, mission and vision of an organisation. ChildRescue, however, aims at being of assistance to the processes as they currently take place. That is why even though BPR is mentioned and up to a point analysed for the sake of completeness of the analysis, there will be no further mention of it. BPM and change management on the other hand, are the techniques that are closely connected to ChildRescue.

As mentioned in the sections above, BPM is occurring when the existing processes are slightly altered in order to achieve the same results in an optimised manner, while change management is how the human capital reacts and adapts to those changes. ChildRescue aims at being a driver of change, however this change is to happen in a non-intrusive manner. The proposed platform that is one of the main outcomes of the project will be a facilitator for SoC, REDCROSS and CF, available to assist the

already involved parties in the process of searching for a missing child or an unaccompanied migrant minor.

2.1.3 Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness

The meaning of the terms Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness may be perceived as totally irrelevant; however, they do share some common characteristics, specifically when seen under the scope of ChildRescue. In this section, an attempt to describe the aforementioned concepts with respect to CR is presented, along with a description of how these concepts will be utilised in order to add as much value as possible to the current missing children investigation processes and to the identification of unaccompanied minors.

2.1.3.1 Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing

The term crowdsourcing was invented by Jeff Howe and Mark Robinson in the June 2006 issue of Wired magazine⁴. They claimed that crowdsourcing is “a new web-based business model that harnesses the creative solutions of a distributed network of individuals through what amounts to an open call for proposals” [19]. Etymologically it is formulated by the words: crowd, referring to the people participating in an initiative, and sourcing, referring to all practices aimed at finding, evaluating and engaging suppliers of goods and services [20].

It is a concept that may be utilised in various occasions and can be given a plethora of definitions. For example, Wikipedia is considered to be a typical example of crowdsourcing according to [21], whereas [22] clearly claim the opposite. Definitions of crowdsourcing as they are most commonly encountered in the literature are presented in the table below.

Definitions	Sources
“the act of taking a job traditionally performed by a designated agent (usually an employee) and outsourcing it to an undefined, generally large group of people in the form of an open call.”	[23]
“a strategic model to attract an interested, motivated crowd of individuals capable of providing solutions superior in quality and quantity to those that even traditional forms of business can.”	[19]
“new online distributed problem-solving and production model in which networked people collaborate to complete a task.”	[24]
“the opening of the innovation process of a firm to integrate numerous and disseminated outside competencies through web facilities”. These competencies can be those of individuals (for example creative people, scientists, engineers) or existing organised communities (for example open source software communities).	[25]

⁴ <https://www.wired.com/2006/06/crowds/>

Table 2-1 Crowdsourcing literature definitions

From the above cited definitions, as well as from a literature review under the context of this deliverable, derives that crowdsourcing involves a large group of people as potential contributors; and crowdsourcing's clear goal is to provide a solution to a problem of an organisation or business.

According to [26], crowdsourcing is differentiated from other, similar forms of participatory user-generated content activities as it entails a mix of top-down and bottom-up management processes that involve a community. Sometimes, little work being done by a lot of people - instead of much work being done by a few people - is more valuable and successful; and crowdsourcing is based on that fact. It is a distributed problem-solving model [27], in which work is divided between participants to achieve a cumulative result.

- In the Boston Marathon bombings, on April 2013, in addition to the usual call for any information leading to possible suspects, the FBI requested citizens to submit any audio-visual material such as videos and photos from the scene of the finish line, where the bombs went off. FBI collected a lot of data from the users, that along with the security video footage taken from nearby buildings lead to the tracking and later to the arrest of the two primary suspects [26].
- Tomnod is a project that uses crowdsourcing to identify important missing objects or people and to mention interesting places in satellite images. Users have access to satellite images and are given the option to tag anything they perceive as peculiar or to add in an image. That is helpful specifically in the case that there is an on-going effort of locating missing people or objects. It can be utilised for instance in the search of a missing or injured climber on a mountain, in the search of locating refugee camps in Somalia, or in the search of Malaysia Airlines Flight 370 debris, etc. [28].

Below some crowdsourcing representative examples with social impact are given:

- In the Boston Marathon bombings, on April 2013, in addition to the usual call for any information leading to possible suspects, the FBI requested citizens to submit any audio-visual material such as videos and photos from the scene of the finish line, where the bombs went off. FBI collected a lot of data from the users, that along with the security video footage taken from nearby buildings led to the tracking and later to the arrest of the two primary suspects [26].
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Obviously, as a mode of sourcing, but not with this specific term itself, crowdsourcing existed prior to the digital age. Regarding the present deliverable and the missing children's cases, missing children's response organisations are aware of the advantages of crowdsourcing. While the crowdsourcing term hadn't been coined in 1996, when Amber Alert was first launched, Amber Alert is a way of

crowdsourcing, since it is based on the provision of quick, accurate and detailed information to citizens on a missing child case, a few minutes after the reporting of the case to the police or the missing children organisation⁵. In the beginning, several actors were communicating the details of the missing child and other basic information through the mass media, SMSs, announcements in airports, subways, highways, etc.

Mobile crowdsourcing

In the past years, the growth of smartphones has given the opportunity for many new concepts to emerge [29]. One of them is mobile crowdsourcing, referring to crowdsourcing activities taking place via smartphones or other mobile devices. This phenomenon has been enabled due to the improvement of smartphone's technological features, including a reliable GPS, internet connectivity, high definition cameras, and the continuous launch of new apps⁶.

The aforementioned improved technological features have provided the users with a plethora of options, thus providing mobile crowdsourcing apps with real-time data and live information⁶. The instant access of the user to their smartphone is another feature that when combined with the location sensors, can be a valuable tool in the process of gathering real-time data. Specifically in ChildRescue's case users will be able to contribute to the missing child search at any time, since according to relevant research smartphone owners carry their phones with them all day long [30]. Of course, to be able to get this kind of information from users, it is necessary to get their consent, making it mandatory for them to accept the terms and conditions, before downloading the mobile app.

Active or passive - or else participatory or opportunistic respectively [31] - collection of data are the two main categories that the data gathered from a mobile crowdsourcing app can fall under. Passive mobile crowdsourcing is when the user gives permission to an app to collect data from their mobile device without requiring any further action from the user. Active collection of data in mobile crowdsourcing requires the active involvement of individuals. In the ChildRescue case the users will be required to actively share data, meaning that they will have to actively participate in the gathering data process.

At this point some statistical data about the usage of smartphones and their penetration will be provided. According to studies⁷, carried out in 2017, smartphone owners spend on their mobile phones over 4 hours a day. Also, a typical smartphone user touches their phone approximately 2.617 times every day⁸, but also reaches for their phone approximately 150 times a day⁸. On 2014, the percentage of smartphone users in the population was 39.1% in Central & Eastern Europe and 57.4% in Western Europe⁹. On 2018, the percentage of the population using smartphones is expected to be 65.3% in Central & Eastern Europe and 78.6% in Western Europe, while on 2019, the number of users is expected rise to a 68.4% and 80.5% in the respective regions⁹. The user engagement on smartphones

⁵ <https://www.hamogelo.gr/gr/en/eksafanisma-paidia:ambert-alert-hellas/>

⁶ <https://www.clickworker.com/crowdsourcing-glossary/mobile-crowdsourcing/>

⁷ <https://hackernoon.com/how-much-time-do-people-spend-on-their-mobile-phones-in-2017-e5f90a0b10a6>

⁸ <https://blog.dscout.com/mobile-touches>

⁹ https://insights.ap.org/uploads/images/eMarketer_Estimates_2015.pdf

tends to grow, thus making the addition of mobile crowdsourcing in the current processes a reasonable next step to facilitate the search of missing children or locating unaccompanied minors.

ChildRescue contribution

In missing children cases time is the worst enemy as the first hours are the most decisive in locating the missing child. One of the most effective actions that the missing children's response organisations can perform, is to immediately alert the crowd that a child has gone missing. Let alone to send specific alerts to users who are close to where the child was last seen or close to the points of interest where the missing child is more likely to be found.

ChildRescue intention is to go one step further compared to the way investigations for a missing child are currently held, by seizing the opportunity smartphones' features provide, since, they have penetrated every aspect of daily life and there is an opportunity to engage the crowd to solve a problem through an open call. The ambition of ChildRescue project is the creation of an innovative solution that enables evidence-based collaborative action during the search and identification of missing children, alerting, and empowering citizens to provide information for identifying the location of a missing child.

The challenge is to quickly find a missing child and the open call could be either Amber Alert or a "Publicity" action, which becomes known to smartphone users, among others, through the platform. Instant alerts are sent to users (depending on their location) when necessary. Then, if they are able, they provide information regarding a missing child's case. Thus, ChildRescue takes advantage of mobile crowdsourcing for real-time and location-sensitive tasks. Reporting live information and being able to use this information immediately fits well with the instantaneity that smartphones provide.

ChildRescue solution primarily engages the smartphone app users - and secondarily the website users - who will have installed the app on their device, and who will be able to receive location-based alerts. It creates a community of volunteer citizens who will act as "investigation social sensors" with the assistance of an easy-to-use platform. They will be able to do so, solely by paying attention to people passing by, thus contributing, and/or validating potential evidence about the missing child's whereabouts.

Instant mobile alerts as well as updates, containing all necessary real-time information about the missing child's profile, are spread to all citizens who are in proximate areas where the missing child was last seen or in areas based on the possible routes the missing child could have taken.

By paying some attention to their surroundings, the users could provide information of crucial importance that could potentially lead to the missing child's location. If a citizen is conscious of the location or has any clue about the missing child, they can either contact the missing children's response organisation or the authorities or they can easily submit any information they have to share to the ChildRescue platform along with potential evidence (e.g. testimony). Such evidence allows other nearby citizens and rescue teams to "crowd-validate" it, so the consistency of reported information is increased, thus optimising the investigation process. Overall, users' information will strengthen the current investigation efforts.

Additionally, before the development of smartphones' industry, the only way for a missing children's response organization to instantly and personally alert its users about a case was by sending an SMS to their phones. But, SMS's technology includes only text. Links that can be clicked and redirect users to a website where they could see more information about a missing child's case, cannot be included to the text message. Images or any other multimedia information that might be helpful can't be

included.¹⁰ However, Amber Alerts or “Publicity” actions are more effective if they are accompanied by more information about a missing child. In ChildRescue platform, it is feasible to publish information such as pictures (as many as necessary), whereas it is not easy to do the same e.g. at the printed posters, on the alerts on highways, or on television.

Instantly sending the alerts to specific users, depending on where they are, in relation to where the child might be, will be more effective, because it is more likely for a user to see a missing child (and therefore help) if the user’s current location lies near the estimated potential location of the missing child. Furthermore, if people do not watch/hear the Amber Alert or a “Publicity action when it is displayed by media, such as TV, radio, etc. they may never notice a missing child’s case. By sending targeted alerts to its users, ChildRescue makes sure that its users are notified about a missing child’s case.

[32] conducted a research about the attention customers pay to posters of missing children at the exits of supermarkets, and the results strengthen ChildRescue’s proposed approach. The aforementioned results indicate that the public considers missing children an important social issue. However, most customers either don’t look or only briefly look at the posters. Thus, they do not memorise the children’s pictures and if they randomly see the missing child on the street, the most likely scenario is that they will pass by without even noticing it. ChildRescue tries to eliminate this problem. Mobile app users can see missing children’s pictures any time they want. That way, if they don’t remember the child’s characteristics, the users can easily refer to the app and by seeing again the picture of the child, they will be able to simultaneously compare and contrast the picture of the missing child with a child that they may see on the street and believe it may be a missing child.

2.1.3.2 *Social Innovation*

Social innovation

The accurate definition of social innovation firstly requires to recognise the ambiguity of the term, as it varies according to the definitions attributed to both the concepts “social” and “innovation” [33].

Social innovation is traced back to the beginning of 19th century, where Godin, explained that the term emerged after the French revolution and, it had both a positive (linked to social reforms) and a negative (synonymous with radical socialism) meaning. Slowly, the social innovation concept was less frequently used and the term “innovation” was more commonly connected to technology. It re-emerged in theoretical writings in the 1960–1970s, and in the last approximately 10 years, many scholars and ultimately the EU, are interested in it, [33]. It had re-emerged as a term that contrasted social innovation with technological innovation and in this respect, it calls for action, to pay more attention to the social aspects of innovation. It is different than business innovation which is generally generated by profit maximisation [34]; social innovation initiates by the need to benefit society by solving societal problems and by engaging citizens in participating in such innovations.

With respect to this deliverable, - as well as the CAPS (Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation) which is analysed below -, social innovation does not contradict technological

¹⁰ <https://www.marketplace.org/2017/12/07/tech/send-or-not-send-emergency-alert>

innovation but, on the contrary, technology is considered as a tool for supporting social innovation [33]. Furthermore, EU's intent is to nurture social innovation by finding new ways to meet social needs which are not adequately met by the market or the public sector¹¹.

There is a plethora of social innovation definitions in the literature, some of them are presented in the table below.

Definitions	Sources
"new products, services or methods that tackle pressing and emerging social issues and, at the same time, transform social interactions promoting new collaboration and relationships"	[33]
"innovative activities and services that are motivated by the goal of meeting a social need and that are predominantly developed and diffused through organisations whose primary purposes are social."	[34]
"Social innovation is an important new field which should be nurtured. It is about tapping into the ingenuity of charities, associations, and social entrepreneurs to find new ways of meeting social needs which are not adequately met by the market or the public sector. It can also be about tapping into this same ingenuity to bring about the behavioural changes which are needed to tackle the major societal challenges, such as climate change. As well as meeting social needs and tackling societal challenges, social innovations empower people and create new social relationships and models of collaboration. They are thus innovative in themselves and good for society's capacity to innovate."	European Commission ¹¹
"Social innovations are changes in the cultural, normative or regulative structures [or classes] of the society which enhance its collective power resources and improve its economic and social performance."	[35]
"Unlike the terms social entrepreneurship and social enterprise, social innovation transcends sectors, levels of analysis, and methods to discover the processes—the strategies, tactics, and theories of change—that produce lasting impact."	[36]

Table 2-2 Social innovation literature definitions

Digital social innovation

Digital Social Innovation (DSI) brings together two prominent trends— new digital technologies and innovation aiming at creating a social impact. It leverages ICT for addressing societal and environmental challenges by pursuing synergies between both the public and the private sectors, as well as by involving citizens as co-creators of solutions [37].

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/innovation-union-communication_en.pdf

People are considered as carriers of knowledge, which can be further exploited through ICT. Online collaboration platforms can play a crucial role in unlocking this implicit knowledge, by allowing citizens to contribute to societal challenges [37]. DSI aims to¹²:

- Improve lives and reorient technology towards more social ends through harnessing ICT,
- empower citizens to use their collective knowledge in order to create a positive impact.

Nowadays, there are some organisations that promote social innovation; Nesta is one of them. It is a UK's innovation foundation which aims to support innovation for the public good [38], and is jointly with the EU developing "Digital Social Innovation for Europe - DSI4EU" which is a research project aiming at fostering efforts of stakeholders interested in this approach [37].

DSI stands at the intersection of three terms: digital, social and innovation. The social dimension includes the notion that technology is a means to addressing social challenges [37]. Some definitions of DSI are presented in the table below.

Definitions	Sources
"Just as digital platforms are changing how we work, shop and have fun, there's a new opportunity for communities to become a part of decision making processes and tackle social challenges. Technology is being used to mobilise the crowd, pool resources and engage the creativity of the general public. We call this phenomenon DSI"	Peter Baeck, NESTA's head of collaborative economy research ¹³ .
DSI is "a type of social and collaborative innovation in which innovators, users and communities collaborate using digital technologies to co-create knowledge and solutions for a wide range of social needs and at a scale and speed that was unimaginable before the rise of the Internet".	[38]

Table 2-3 Digital social innovation literature definitions

Additionally, [39] identified six primary domains of digital social innovation: 1. The Collaborative Economy, 2. New ways of sensing, 3. Open democracy, 4. Awareness networks, 5. Open Access, 6. Funding and Incubation. Awareness networks are also a set target of ChildRescue. Dissemination has already started, and as months go by, the communication strategy is strengthened so that the ChildRescue initiative can be made known to the public. Several promotion campaigns have been implemented (website, social media, blog post) to raise awareness.

As far as the EU is concerned, DSI4EU which is supported by the European Union and funded under the Horizon 2020 Programme, is part of the CAPS (which is analysed below) community. It supports and grows the current DSI network of projects and organisations¹⁴. Currently, 1047 projects and 1957 organisations have been engaged with DSI¹⁵. Of course, ChildRescue is one of them.

¹² <https://digitalsocial.eu/about-the-project>

¹³ <https://www.pioneerspost.com/news-views/20170721/how-digital-social-innovation-re-engaging-people-politics>

¹⁴ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/dsi4eu/>

¹⁵ <https://digitalsocial.eu/projects>

Below lie some examples of social innovation:

- The Internet to this day is one of the biggest social innovations. Everyone can participate in what the Internet offers (e.g. information, social media, communication, and games)¹⁶.
- Ushahidi platform's mission is twofold: to help marginalized people raise their voice and to make the community listen to them and respond better¹⁷. It is often used for crisis response, citizen reporting/government accountability, and human rights reporting¹⁸. It was employed in response to the Haiti Earthquake in 2010, (Ushahidi–Haiti Project) [40], and was also used to monitor violence in the Syrian civil war (Syria Tracker Crisis Map)¹⁹.
- ForestWatchers project tries to address the problem of fires and illegal logging. Individuals (locals, volunteers, NGOs, etc.) from all around the world, monitor selected patches of forest across the globe, almost in real-time, by using a notebook, a tablet or a smartphone connected to the Internet. They do not need to have scientific training but they just perform or manage research-related tasks such as observation, measurement, or computation²⁰.

Of course, there is always the possibility of DSI initiatives to fail. Few out of the hundreds of DSI initiatives across Europe have grown to deliver positive social impact on a scale - and none has approached the comparable growth of commercial digital platforms²¹.

Some indicative reasons digital social innovations fail are²²:

- projects and organisations involved in DSI are relatively poorly connected to each other,
- lack of funding and digital skills' shortage,
- adoption of established civil society organisations is too slow,
- conflict and lack of commitment between the partners.

So, there is much work to be done. The European Commission - a longstanding supporter of DSI - offered funding (through the €65 million CAPS programme) so that DSI4EU can continue its work till August 2019. There are several challenges to be tackled, such as²³:

- stakeholder engagement; ChildRescue success is directly dependent on the number of users that will be engaged – that is why the dissemination and communication efforts have already started from an early stage in the project,
- not enough understanding of growth routes and business models; ChildRescue organised a workshop in the 1st Plenary meeting on the ChildRescue business model to explore the existing possibilities, though from the outset, the project is not profit oriented,

¹⁶ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/news/everyday-social-innovations/world-wide-web>

¹⁷ <https://www.ushahidi.com/about>

¹⁸ <https://techrasam.org/2017/07/06/ushahidi-a-data-collection-monitoring-and-visualization-software-for-the-humanitarian-and-development-industry/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ushahidi.com/case-studies/syria-tracker>

²⁰ <http://forestwatchers.net/mission.html>

²¹ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/taking-digital-social-innovation-to-the-next-level/>

²² <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/what-next-for-digital-social-innovation-realising-the-potential-of-people-and-technology-to-tackle-social-challenges/>

²³ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/thousands-of-people-are-using-technology-to-tackle-social-challenges-but-whats-holding-digital-social-innovation-back/>

- cooperation between the partners; ChildRescue partners cooperate harmoniously so far, although there are different points of views, as is normal with so many different countries and scientific backgrounds. The convergence of different processes is also hindered by the different organisations' operations, the different practices and principles that they follow, and their vision. These differences are solved by discussion at the frequent teleconferences and Plenary meetings.

ChildRescue contribution

As ChildRescue contributes with its methodology and the online platform in finding missing children, it provides both a product, i.e. ChildRescue platform, but it also suggests - among others - a new process, that will enhance the current process of locating missing children. This way, ChildRescue is consistent with the [33] definition, as it offers both a product (platform) and a service (methodology). Additionally, according to the DSI description above, ChildRescue lies in the intersection of digital technology (platform), innovation process (platform and methodology), and society (challenge of finding missing children).

It aims to be an additional tool to the missing children's response organisations, which will enhance their efforts, by harnessing people's existing knowledge about the possible whereabouts of a missing child. By instantly sending alerts to the users who have installed the app on their smartphones and they are in a specific radius near the possible location of the child, it is possible to have human sensors that may see the child and report that to the competent authorities. ChildRescue evaluates the incoming information, e.g. possible viewing of the missing child, adjusting accordingly its investigation efforts.

Moreover, ChildRescue aims to add and integrate in its platform more organisations (across Europe) that provide services similar to the services that REDCROSS or SoC provides to immigrants-minors or that contribute to the investigations of missing children. In this way, ChildRescue creates a communication channel between organisations that have similar objectives, or those whose objectives could be combined, achieving more effective collaboration between them. ChildRescue aim is that the SoC pilots use REDCROSS's pilots and vice versa. That way, better cooperation and understanding of the organisations' procedures will be achieved. The exploitation of the features, resources, and networks of each organisation that is part of ChildRescue will be mutually used by the organisations in either a missing child emergency case or in the discovery and identification case of unaccompanied minors.

2.1.3.3 Collective Awareness

Collective awareness

Collective awareness, combined with new technologies, can be supportive in cases that information coming from the public could be of high value. Missing person investigations are such cases.

According to [38], collective awareness platforms (collective intelligence) and crowdsourcing are in the scope of DSI. One solving problems strategy is the top-down, whereas its opposite is the bottom-up strategy. These platforms take advantage of the latter, where knowledge is harnessed from the participating community.

There isn't a unique definition for collective awareness, similar to the case of crowdsourcing and social innovation. The term was introduced by the French sociologist Émile Durkheim in his Division of Labour

in Society in 1893, in which he defines collective consciousness, or else collective awareness (French: conscience collective) as "the body of beliefs and sentiments common to the average of members of a society" [41].

With the ICT development, the term "collective awareness" has been revised and rephrased under several perspectives (e.g. human-computer interaction, computer-supported collaborative work, etc.) [42] and several definitions have been proposed, depending on the adopted perspective. Some proposed representative collective awareness definitions which reflect its evolution, along with alternative terms describing neighbouring concepts with that of collective awareness - which is mainly adopted by the European Commission -, such as collective intelligence, wisdom of the crowd, lie on the table below.

	Definition	Source
Collective Awareness	"Collective awareness refers to a common and shared vision of the whole team's context which allows members to coordinate implicitly their activities and behaviours through communication".	[43]
	"The Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation (CAPS) are ICT systems leveraging the emerging 'network effect' by combining open online social media, distributed knowledge creation and data from real environments ('Internet of Things') in order to create awareness of problems and possible solutions requesting collective efforts, enabling new forms of social innovation."	European Commission ²⁴ [33]
Collective Intelligence	"Collective Intelligence is built on the concept that when large groups of individuals cooperate higher-order intelligence, solutions and innovation can be produced while coming to function as a new individual entity, appearing to have a mind of its own."	[44]
Wisdom of the Crowd	Wisdom of crowds is based on the idea that "a group will not always give you the right answer but that on average it will consistently come up with a better answer than any individual could provide"	[45]

Table 2-4 Definitions relevant with the term Collective Awareness

In the context of the present deliverable, the approach of the EC is adopted, where collective awareness is achieved through ICT systems leveraging the network effect. ChildRescue ambition is based on the same background; creating an ICT platform that harnesses the network effect; the more users use it, the more effective it is.

CAPS

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/events/collective-awareness-platforms-sustainability-and-social-innovation-information-day_en

CAPS (Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation) is a Horizon 2020 programme funded by the EC and launched in 2013, which has the aim of helping grassroots initiatives that contribute to societal change by harnessing the existing but also the emerging network technologies, by mainly using a bottom-up strategy [38].

CAPS initiative is pioneering new models to raise awareness of emerging challenges and of the role that people can play to ease them through collective action. It aims at developing online platforms to raise awareness on sustainability problems and implementing collective solutions. Its objective is to harness the collaborative power of ICT networks to create collective awareness alongside with enabling collective solutions. CAPS approach is based upon: 1. Taking advantage of the ICT network effects, e.g. using crowdsourcing, thus achieving collective intelligence, integrating human networks; 2. Setting sustainability as a goal, targeting beyond profit, tackling social challenges²⁵.

CAPS intend to enable citizens to²⁶:

- share their knowledge,
- make better informed decisions,
- create more participatory processes.

Some CAPS projects relevant to ChildRescue are²⁷:

- MAZI: a DIY networking toolkit for location-based collective awareness,
- CAP4Access: methods and tools for collectively gathering and sharing spatial information for improving accessibility,
- Families_Share: a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance.

Regarding the motivation of why a user should use CAPS, the [46] results showed that social identity (18%), social comparison (18%), and altruism (17%) are the main motives. Monetary incentives (14%) and social approval (11%) follow. Desirability bias (9%), gamification (7%) and reputation (5%) give less incentive to users to use CAPS.

ChildRescue contribution

Compassion and the urge to be of assistance when there is a need are elements of the human nature. Collective efforts of individuals can contribute to the improvement of society [47]. ChildRescue is based on that concept, taking advantage of this natural trend, giving the users the opportunity to altruistically do something for the common good, find a missing child, which is inherently a collaborative task [48].

In the aforementioned paragraph some of the motivations why a user would use CAPS, are presented. Sometimes people want to selflessly contribute to societal problems without necessarily seeking for financial profit, but they lack the knowhow or the means to do so. Such a problem is the missing children cases. Today, people contribute to missing children cases by informing the competent authorities if they have some information about a missing child, either from their social media profiles or if they just randomly see them. This cannot be changed. ChildRescue added value is that it makes it

²⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/collective-awareness-platforms-sustainability-and-social-innovation-caps>

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/collective-awareness>

²⁷ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/>

possible for the users - combining the collective awareness-intelligence concept with geo-fencing techniques to engage users according to their location - to instantly have all the necessary information about a case, with them all the time, so that if there is an opportunity, they could be of assistance to such cases. Thus, the solution comes from the users' collective intelligence.

Finally, ChildRescue is a CAPS project²⁸, based on the bottom-up strategy, which aims at effectively and timely raising collective awareness during the investigation of missing children as well as supporting the identification of missing unaccompanied refugee minors. It also:

- gives people the opportunity to contribute in the investigation process of locating the missing children, encouraging them to share the existing knowledge they have,
- harnesses information from the crowd, which otherwise might be omitted, so that the location of the missing children is found more quickly,
- make better decisions considering the people's testimonies.

2.1.4 Behavioural and Activity Profiling Theories and Research Review

While cases of missing persons, especially missing children, receive a lot of media attention, research on the topic of finding missing persons is scarce, especially within Europe. While there have been studies on the impact of the amber alert in the US, there is a lack of research for the European continent, with the exception of Shalev Green/Hedges study on the usefulness of child alert systems in the Netherlands, UK, Czech Republic and Poland [49], which found out that experts on the field agreed that the Internet and Social Media were rather effective in both raising awareness about as well as recovering a missing child [49].

Additionally, 16-24-year olds reported in 2016 to spend on average 29 hrs/week on the internet and 99 per cent reported using social media at least once a week, with social media accounting for 27 per cent of their total communication time [50]. Comparing data over time, the usage of social media from adolescents seems to be increasing, rendering a social media analysis increasingly useful in understanding and predicting behavioural patterns of children and adolescents, which has been utilised by market research to predict spending patterns or health studies to gain insights into risk behavior [51]. With children and adolescents spending more and more time on the internet and specifically on social media applications, the analysis of social media data should be utilised in the search for missing children to predict potential points of interest.

However, while the sheer mass of data generated constantly, offers a unique opportunity to understanding individual choices as well as social group dynamics that can assist in identifying the location of missing persons, data mining is needed in order to make sense of the data pool. Thus, "Data mining research has successfully produced numerous methods, tools, and algorithms for handling large amounts of data to solve real-world problems. Therefore, data mining has become an integral part of many application domains including bioinformatics, data warehousing, business intelligence, predictive analytics, and decision support systems. The primary objectives of the data mining process are to effectively handle large-scale data, extract actionable patterns, and gain insightful knowledge. Nowadays, social media is widely used for various purposes. Vast amounts of user-generated data exist and it can be made available for various kinds of analysis. There is no doubt that to utilize such data in

²⁸ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/childrescue/>

social media is the key to improve various business processes” [52]. Data mining processes utilise the so-called ‘big data’, which are “proliferating and complex data sets that can be open or shared online” [53]. Through the increased use of smart phones and social media more specifically, and the vast amount of data willingly shared by individuals with the public, the analysis of big data becomes increasingly relevant [51] and can be adopted to help find missing persons. However, as there is still a severe lack of research on the use of social media analysis through a computer based big data analysis or sentiment analysis, this report will refer to connected fields of interest and findings from those areas as well as studies on child alert systems more generally.

Additionally, while sentiment analysis or general big data analysis is crucial for the recovery of missing children, the underlying theory needed for the correct prediction of behaviour based on online interactions is the network theory, specifically the activity theory as well as the subcultural theory. Both the activity theory as well as the subcultural theory focus on the importance of social interaction for individual decision-making processes. However, the subcultural theory, which follows the school of thought of Cohen (1955), who observed that youth in gang structures obeyed to different norms and valued certain behaviours with respect to whether they were looked down upon in mainstream society, is forming a separate subculture with alternative norms and values [54]. This can offer a valuable insight into the behaviour of runaway youths as well as refugee minors, who have been reported missing, as they often find themselves in unofficial networks with deviant behavioural rules. As children and adolescents are heavily influenced by the norms of their groups of friends, or social networks [55], the analysis of those networks and their respective norms and rules is essential for a successful prediction of behaviour.

In contrast, the activity theory focusses more on the interaction of humans and the way those shape individual behaviour. “Activity theory centres on mediation and the concept that the way humans undertake an activity is influenced by the environment around them and their ability to develop an understanding based upon previous experiences in order to make logical actions. This mediation is man-made in that the tools which influence a subject have been developed by the subject or other people who have previously worked in the same context” [56]. Thus, the empirical approach to identifying potential points of interest for the children is intrinsically linked to a theoretical base that centres on the relationship between the individual actor and their (social) environment.

While most cases of children who were reported missing have either run away or been abducted by a non-custodial parent [57], all cases are time-sensitive as the risk of victimisation of the child increases over time. In cases of child abductions that result in murder, almost half of the victims are killed within the first hour of the abduction and close to 80 per cent are murdered within three hours of being taken, making a quick recovery a matter of life and death [58]. In these time sensitive scenarios, the question of the most effective approach to analysing the data and spreading the information to the most crucial people arises. As “[h]umans have a limited amount of time per day to dedicate to social interaction, which poses a limit on the effort one can invest in persuading an acquaintance to act. Further, time pressure can affect the way in which people process environmental information. Consequently, people may be expected to resort to so-called blind search, focusing simply on the recruitment of as many acquaintances as possible via broadcast messaging. However, while this strategy may be effective at delivering the message to a broad audience, it results in lower effort in finding and mobilizing those recruits that have high affinity with the task (due to their location or other characteristics), and are therefore more likely to propagate the message or participate in the required action” [59]. In the [59]

study, which used the social media app Twitter, the team was able to find three of the five actors who posed as 'thieves' all over Europe and the US within 12 hours and with only a staged mugshot to distribute, by utilising social media and a "recursive incentive mechanism that encourages recruitment" [59]. Consequently, ChildRescue aims at targeting points of interests and the people located there as they can be considered to have the described high affinity with the task and to combine predictive methods of analysing the data of the social media accounts with the effort of targeted recruitment. There are a variety of algorithms available to analyse mass data, such as social media data, which is currently mostly used for market analysis purposes but could be projected onto other topics. The following graphic shows different categories of analysis and the corresponding variety of algorithms to choose from depending on the method that is most appropriate for the research, giving an insight into the variety of possibilities:

Categories of analysis and selection of algorithms	
<i>categories of analysis</i>	<i>algorithms (examples)</i>
classification	Decision Trees, Neural Networks, Bayesian Models, Induction Rules, K-Nearest Neighbours
Regression	Linear Regression, Non-Linear Regression, Logistic Regression
Anomaly Detection	Distance based, Density based, Local outlier Factor (LOF)
Time Series	Exponential Smoothing, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Regression
Clustering	K-Means, Density based Clustering
Association Analysis	Frequent Pattern Growth (FP-Growth) Algorithm, Apriori Algorithm

Table 2-5 Different Categories of analysis and corresponding algorithms [60]

ChildRescue contribution

For the ChildRescue project, the differentiation between cases of missing children, as suggested by Missing Children Europe (MCE), in runaways, abductions by third persons, (international) parental abductions and missing unaccompanied minors [61] is followed. The phenomenon of missing children is thus one of a vast variety that calls for nuanced approaches and cannot be explained with a 'one-fits-all' solution. Hence, the ChildRescue project will advance the theoretical understanding and the timely solution of missing children cases by utilising various theoretical approaches to enlighten the situation. ChildRescue will operate with state of the art knowledge through literature review to collect best practice examples, which are being relined with different theoretical approaches to the topic in order to provide the appropriate academic foundation. Albeit summarised under the same umbrella term of missing children, abductions and runaways need different theoretical approaches to account

for differing levels of urgency and threat. Although some theories, such as the social network theory, might be applied to various case types, different aspects of the theory will be in focus. For example, in the case of runaways, the social network theory could be utilised to find out more about the key people in the adolescent's life in order to establish points of interest or potential contact sources, while the social network theory can also be applied to cases of third-person abduction to gain a better understanding of grooming processes online. Additionally, the theories can be linked to computational strategies, such as sentiment analysis or graph theories to be utilised in a practical application as envisioned by the ChildRescue project. The following table will illustrate theories that might be useful in the explanation of these phenomena and could be applied in the course of the ChildRescue project:

Categories of missing children cases and theories	
<i>Missing children case type</i>	<i>Theories (examples)</i>
Runaways	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Third-person abductions	Social Network Theory, Victimology
Parental Abductions	Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Missing unaccompanied minors	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Collective Behaviour Theory

Table 2-6 Different types of missing children cases and appropriate theories

Task 2.1 will provide the theoretical and methodological framing for the profiling of missing children in the ChildRescue project by completing a literature review as step one (Figure 2-4), which will identify gaps in knowledge and establish a state of the art pre-selection of theories as step two (Table 2-6). The identified gaps will in turn serve to select fitting interviewees, namely experts in the field (step three), who can provide case studies of the different types of missing children scenarios identified in table 2. After the completion of the interviews and the analysis of the provided case studies, the preselection of theories will be reduced to the most appropriate explanations for the different case types in step four. Simultaneously, this will inform the updated theoretical framework of the ChildRescue project that can in turn add to the existing literature in the field. The literature review will be updated regularly throughout the term of the project to incorporate the latest state of the art knowledge on missing children research. This will in turn inform the methodology of the profiling of missing children, which will be based on the experience of experts in the field.

Figure 2-4 Workflow Chart WP 2.1

2.2 ChildRescue-relevant Technologies and Systems

2.2.1 Technologies and Systems for Missing People Identification

Private and public organizations all over the world have developed or adapted systems for designing and managing missing persons cases. Several examples of systems are included below:

1. National Missing and Unidentified Persons System (NamUs)

Operator / Developer: National Forensic Science Technology Centre

NamUs is an online, national centralised repository and resource center for missing persons and unidentified decedent records. NamUs can be searched by medical examiners, coroners, law enforcement officials and the general public from all over the country in hopes of resolving these cases.

Availability and Cost: Free, but some sections are available only to public safety personnel.

Downloads/Links: Access databases (requires registration): <https://www.namus.gov/Dashboard#>

Potential use in the project: That system can provide ideas for a variety of resources and uses for child rescue. For example, functions as (a) the ability to print missing persons' posters, (b) to receive free biometric collection and testing assistance and (c) links to medical examiner and law enforcement agencies could be useful.

2. National Emergency Child Locator Center (NECLC)

Operator / Developer: National Centre for Missing & Exploited Children (NCMEC)

NCMEC activates the NECLC to manage calls and a database relating to missing children for the event. Individuals reporting or searching for a child missing as a result of a disaster can call the NECLC at 1-866-908-9570 or 1-877-908-9570. NECLC is only activated at the request of a State to support Presidentially-declared disasters.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: The NECLC can be accessed at <https://www.missingkids.org/disasterresponse>.

Potential use in the project: the function of family reunification.

3. American Red Cross Safe and Well website

Operator / Developer: American Red Cross

The American Red Cross Safe and Well website is a free communication tool where survivors can register and post messages to indicate that they are safe, and where their family, friends, and colleagues can conduct a search to view those posted messages. During large-scale disasters, the site is heavily promoted in the media and at local call centres. Safe and Well will also be set as the home page on computers at Red Cross congregate centres and shelters in host and evacuation areas. The website is available in English and Spanish and has also been configured for smart phones, including Blackberry, Apple, and Android devices. Safe and Well users can update statuses on Facebook and via Twitter. The site is always available and can be used by the public. Safe and Well can be accessed at <http://www.redcross.org/safeandwell>.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: Safe and Well can be accessed at

<https://safeandwell.communityyos.org/cms/index.php>

Potential use in the project: That system includes the functions of (a) Register (those affected by disaster self-register on the site) and (b) Search friends and family (search the list and view the registrants' posted messages). This function is not considered useful for Child Rescue for the cases of missing children, but it may be useful for UAMs.

4. Restoring Family Links

Operator / Developer: International Committee of the Red Cross

Every year, thousands of family members are separated by conflicts, disasters or migration. People suffer terribly when they lose contact with their loved ones and don't know where they are or whether they are safe.

The ICRC and National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies work together around the world to locate people and put them back into contact with their relatives. This work includes looking for family members, restoring contact, reuniting families, and seeking to clarify the fate of those who remain missing.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: Emergency Welfare Inquiries can be accessed at

<https://familylinks.icrc.org/en/pages/home.aspx>

Potential use in the project: the function of on-line tracing could be further investigated, if it could be useful for Child Rescue.

5. National Emergency Family Registry and Locator System (NEFRLS)

Operator / Developer: Disaster Assistance Improvement Program's (DAIP)

Established in the aftermath of Hurricanes Katrina and Rita, NEFRLS is a nationally-accessible, web-based system that facilitates the reunification of families separated or displaced by a disaster. It allows adults who have been displaced from their homes or pre-incident locations to voluntarily register and share specific information on their post-disaster well-being or location with designated family members. Family members and friends may search the database for a record created by a displaced individual. NEFRLS is activated when requested by a State following a Presidentially-declared disaster or mass evacuation event and operates on a 24/7 basis. It is accessible via 1-800-588-9822.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: www.disasterassistance.gov

Potential use in the project: That system can provide ideas for a variety of resources and uses for child rescue. For example, the functions (a) web - based system where people can voluntarily register and share specific information on their post-disaster well-being or location with specified family members and (b) the SMS service that notifies the individual when an official missing person report has been submitted, could be useful.

6. Lost Person Finder (LPF)

Operator / Developer: The National Library of Medicine (NLM)

The LPF Project focuses on tools and technologies to enable family, friends, and neighbours to locate missing people during a disaster event. The National Library of Medicine (NLM) initially created this web-based people finder software for finding people who were in hospitals after a disaster. After the Haiti earthquake, it was modified to allow public access for community-wide disasters.

- PEOPLE LOCATOR® and ReUnite®—ReUnite is a free iOS/Android app that assists users reunifying families after disasters and can be used by the public to search and report missing or found persons including a field for their health status. Information gathered through this app is uploaded to the PEOPLE LOCATOR website <https://pl.nlm.nih.gov>, which features search and report as well, including an option for interactive notification information scrolling.
- TriageTrak and TriagePic®—Healthcare services providers can use this website (TriageTrak) running on their own infrastructure and free reporting tool (TriagePic) to better respond to inquiries for missing persons after large scale casualty events. Report and search is flexible via Android and iOS apps and, in the enterprise, via a Windows 7 application. Service providers and their partners can help provide faster and more accurate reassurance, and thus facilitate family reunification and enhance coordination with other disaster-responding non-governmental organizations and alleviate some of the workload on public health personnel and other responders who interact with the public.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: For more information, visit:

- ReUnite can be downloaded at <https://lpf.nlm.nih.gov/PeopleLocator-ReUnite>.
- TriageTrak and TriagePic can be downloaded at <https://lpf.nlm.nih.gov/TriageTrak-TriagePic>

Potential use in the project: That system provides functions to seekers to search the database and retrieve the information on their devices. In addition, the system will display pictures and other information on missing persons as well as health care services.

7. Google Crisis Response

Operator / Developer: Google

Person Finder and Crisis Map are Google's primary tools that support reunification. Google Person Finder allows individuals to post and search for the status of relatives or friends affected by a disaster. The program also lets press agencies, NGOs, and others contribute to the Post- Disaster Missing Persons Process database and receive updates by using the Person Finder application programming interface (API) based on the Person Finder Interchange Format (PFIF) open standard. Google Crisis Map provides a map for a specific incident that can show its location and capacity at shelters open for a disaster. Both products can be embedded in websites, and information can be downloaded and shared.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.google.org/crisisresponse/resources.html>.

Potential use in the project: the interoperability methodology among multiple applications (Google Earth, Google Fusion Tables, Google Person Finder, etc.) could be useful.

8. Facebook Safety Check

Operator / Developer: Facebook

Facebook launched its Safety Check feature in 2014 that helps users inform friends and family that ask if they are safe. Users can click the "I'm Safe" button to notify family and friends of their status. The tool does not provide information to anyone other than users' own networks of family and friends.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.facebook.com/about/safetycheck/>

Potential use in the project: the function and methodology of utilising social networks.

9. FBI National Crime Information Center (NCIC)

Operator / Developer: FBI

The NCIC system is an electronic clearinghouse of crime data that can be tapped from virtually every criminal justice agency nationwide. In operation since 1967, NCIC helps criminal justice professionals apprehend fugitives, locate missing persons, recover stolen property, and identify terrorists. This system is divided into 21 files, including a file for missing persons, a national sex offender registry, and an unidentified person's file.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <http://www.fbi.gov/about-us/cjis/ncic>

Potential use in the project: the function, the fields and the methodology of keeping the "Missing Persons File" could be useful.

10. Unidentified Victim Identification System (UVIS)

Operator / Developer: New York City

New York City's UVIS is a comprehensive disaster management system that manages and coordinates all of the activities related to missing persons reporting and victim identification. In concert with New York City's 3-1-1 Call Center, the City of New York Office of Chief Medical Examiner, the New York Police Department, and other agencies throughout the city, UVIS enables a centralised communications and data collection system to support these processes. This coordinated system is essential to developing an accurate manifest of potential victims following a disaster—a critical first step in victim identification.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links:

www.nyc.gov/html/ocme/downloads/pdf/Special%20Operations/UVIS%20Information%20Guide_20090917.pdf.

Potential use in the project: That system can provide ideas for a variety of resources and uses for ChildRescue. For example, the functions (a) Missing Persons module (extremely detailed data filing), (b) Records module (handles requests for records from family members, lawyers, and public administrators) and (c) Field Operation module (helps users manage incidents, field investigation, and the collection of remains and evidence, as well as maintaining records and documentation about remains and evidence) could be useful.

11. 2-1-1 VIRGINIA Patient Locator System

Operator / Developer: 211

In 2010, 2-1-1 VIRGINIA became the call center for the Virginia Hospital and Healthcare Association's Patient Locator and Family Reunification Centers. In a mass casualty event, 2-1-1 VIRGINIA can provide real-time information on the hospital location of victims to family and friends via a system that connects 2-1-1 with Virginia EMS and hospitals.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <http://www.211.org>.

Potential use in the project: That system does fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

12. Radiant RFID

Operator / Developer: Texas Department of Public Safety

The Texas Department of Public Safety has an agreement with Radiant RFID (also known as Evacuation Tracking Network [ETN]) to use their system to track evacuees during a disaster. Evacuees meet at locations known as embarkation centres. Upon arrival, each adult and child is issued a wristband, and pets have tags attached to their collars. Both the pet and child bands are linked to their legal guardians in the database. Buses are equipped with global positioning system (GPS) locators to track the whereabouts of the vehicles and the individuals inside them. As the evacuees disembark the buses, their needs are assessed and a final location destination is determined. Each individual's information is retrieved using a handheld scanner used to scan their wristbands.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <http://www.rfidjournal.com/article/view/4443/2>.

Potential use in the project: the function of tracking and retrieval of information in the field could be useful.

13. Lost Person Locator

Operator / Developer: DHS Science and Technology Directorate

The Department of Homeland Security Science and Technology Directorate (S&T), along with dbS Productions--known as the leading source of search and rescue research, publications, and training--has initiated a program to develop guidance, protocols and strategies responders can employ while searching for lost individuals. Called the Lost Person Locator, these guidelines and data sets will be readily available in an easy-to-follow format. First responders in the field will be able to use the Lost Person Locator software to quickly and safely locate missing people.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: To learn more about the Lost Person Locator, contact: SandTFRG@hq.dhs.gov

Potential use in the project: Currently that software is under development and it is not feasible to obtain more data.

14. Photo Missing Children

Operator / Developer: Microsoft

The Photo Missing Children, or PhotoMC, is an application designed to help find missing children through Microsoft's face recognition application program interface (API). The Microsoft Face API is a cloud-based service that uses advanced algorithms to scan images of faces for identifying features and determines the likelihood that two faces belong to the same person. It can scan a database of thousands of faces and return a list of possible matches within seconds. The API analyzes 27 different facial characteristics and can identify a person across multiple photos, even at different angles and with varying facial expressions.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links:

- <https://news.microsoft.com/features/lost-boy-fathers-search-microsoft-technology-helped-solve-four-year-mystery/>
- <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/cognitive-services/face/>

Potential use in the project: The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

15. The CHARLEY PROJECT

Operator / Developer: The Charley Project

The Charley Project profiles approximately 10,000 "cold case" missing people mainly from the United States. It does not actively investigate cases; it is merely a publicity vehicle for missing people who are often neglected by the press and forgotten all too soon. A person must have been missing for at least one year to be listed.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <http://charleyproject.org>.

Potential use in the project: That system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

16. Database of missing persons and unidentified bodies

Operator / Developer: InterPol

A project is under way to create the first ever police database to identify and link missing persons and unidentified bodies on an international level. The Fast and Efficient International Disaster Victim Identification (FASTID) Project was launched in 2010 with an overall budget of almost EUR 3 million.

Led by INTERPOL and partly funded by the European Commission, the project will establish an international system to manage enquiries concerning missing persons and unidentified bodies in the event of disasters as well as day-to-day policing and will result in the creation of a global Missing Persons and Unidentified Bodies (MPUB) database.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.interpol.int/INTERPOL-expertise/Forensics/DVI-Pages/Database-of-missing-persons-and-unidentified-bodies>

Potential use in the project: Currently that software is under development and it is not feasible to obtain more data.

17. Find People & Things

Operator / Developer: Instituto Superior para as Tecnologias de Informação e Comunicação - Luanda, Angola

This project aims to build an online platform to facilitate the process of finding missing people and objects. For this it is intended to use facial recognition techniques and information search on the platform. Once a person, documents or anything else is missing, the person concerned should go to the platform, submit a picture of the missing person or object accompanied by some information such as the place where the person disappeared. Also, if someone else finds a missing person or object, makes a submission with an image, the data of the person or object and the place where he/she/it was found. After that, it is the platform's responsibility to crosscheck the submission's validity and find all relevant information. If there is no crossover, the platform stores the inserted data, and in case another user finds a person or objects already registered as missing, the system informs the user.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.isutic.gov.ao>

Potential use in the project: The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

18. Face First

Operator / Developer: Face First

FaceFirst provides the best-in-class facial recognition software. With the FaceFirst face recognition platform, retailers, stadiums, transportation centres, law enforcement agencies and other organisations can detect and deter threats in real time, while also leveraging biometric data to personalise service and verify personal identity. Using artificial intelligence and machine learning, FaceFirst is highly accurate and scalable, offering a full range of surveillance, mobile access control and desktop forensic face detection capabilities. FaceFirst offers a robust SDK/API for integration into a variety of systems and platforms.

Availability and Cost: For Non Profit Organisations the licence is free.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.facefirst.com>

Potential use in the project: The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

19. DEVPOST

Operator / Developer: DEVPOST

DEVPOST is a web-based app that allows users to match their cloud photo repositories with a missing person database. Upon confident matches, the app will prompt identifications to the user for further investigation. In detail, the app can:

- Get photo access authorisation from repositories (Google photos for the submission)
- Identify distinct faces in each photo
- Match each face with identities in the databases
- Return photo pairs of 2 similar faces (and mark them)
- Render paired results on the website and allow users to decide if we have a match

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://devpost.com/software/find-missing-people>

Potential use in the project: The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

20. Find My Way Home Project

Operator / Developer: CUE Center for Missing Persons

This page is for persons who either know they were abducted or believe they were abducted, as small children, and raised by their abductors. It is very difficult for these people to come forward publicly for fear of retaliation from their abductor. Sometimes they don't know where to start – they can't remember their real name, where they were born, or anything that would help them find their family. Find My Way Home project is to provide support, raise awareness, and provide resources to help reunite long-term abductees with their birth families. The project is inspired by someone who was abducted as a child and is still searching for her birth family.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <http://www.ncmissingpersons.org/resources-links/find-my-way-home-project/>

Potential use in the project: That system does not fall in the scope of Child Rescue.

21. ICMP Online Inquiry Center

Operator / Developer: ICMP - International Commission on Missing Persons

ICMP's Online Inquiry Center (OIC) is a tool to provide information or obtain information about a missing person. It is an online resource that can be accessed by families of the missing and others.

Developed on the basis of ICMP's long-standing record of helping governments, families of the missing and others, the OIC is a place where concrete and usable information is collected and stored so that it can be utilised when it is needed in the search for missing persons.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://oic.icmp.int/index.php?w=intro>

Potential use in the project: That system can provide ideas for a variety of resources and uses for ChildRescue. For example, the function of Identification Data Management System (iDMS) is a specialised software solution for managing large scale missing persons programs. The iDMS has a set of powerful integrated applications that support the process of storing, viewing and analysing very large amounts of data on missing persons, investigations, and identifications. That system could be useful.

22. LOST - Missing people in Europe

The program is implemented by 8 partners from Italy, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Belgium & Denmark.

LOST is a 2-year European innovative program dealing with the area of action of the response on disappearances, where different kind of professionals working on cases of missing children and adults would benefit from receiving specific training and support by technical operators & VET trainers. These kinds of professionals could be members of law enforcement agencies, the police force, secret services & civil protection, representatives of voluntary associations or NGO, personnel of Public local such as social assistants, psychologists who provide support to families, health professionals & legal doctors.

Downloads/Links: <http://lost.team/#!/project>

Potential use in the project: Currently that software is under development and it is not feasible to obtain more data.

23. National DNA Index System

Operator / Developer: FBI

FBI operates a database that stores DNA records, including missing adults' records and unidentified remains. NDIS contains approximately 15 million profiles in the five databases: offenders and arrestees database, forensic evidence database, missing unidentified human remains database, missing person database, and biological relatives of missing persons database. The biological relatives of missing persons database contains DNA profiles that are voluntarily submitted by the relatives of known missing individuals. Finally, the missing person database contains DNA records of missing persons obtained from their belongings or derived from the profiles of their relatives.

Availability and Cost: It is free but not accessible from the public. It has been foreseen a SOP for the public.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.fbi.gov/services/laboratory/biometric-analysis/codis>

Potential use in the project: That system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

24. Alert Systems (AMBER & SILVER)

Amber Alert systems are voluntary partnerships among law enforcement agencies, broadcasters, and transportation agencies to activate messages in a targeted area when a child is abducted and believed to be in grave danger or a senior is at risk. Silver alert systems were created out of concern for the safety of seniors and other at-risk adult populations who are prone to wandering due to a physical or cognitive disability or medical condition such as Alzheimer's or other forms of dementia.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links:

- <https://www.amberalert.gov/about.htm>
- <https://www.amberalert.eu>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Silver_Alert

Potential use in the project: the function "Wireless Emergency Alert program" of distributing information in multiple means of communication (mobiles, tv, internet, etc.) could be useful.

25. Missing Children Database

Operator / Developer: Canadian Centre for Child Protection

This database contains a listing of nationally-registered missing children in Canada. A case remains open until the child is located.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: https://missingkids.ca/app/en/missing_children_database

Potential use in the project: the function of "Missing-Person Record" in terms of methodology, fields and offline and online methods of research could be useful.

26. The Australian Police Child ID App

Operator / Developer: The National Missing Persons Coordination Centre (NMPCC)

The National Missing Persons Coordination Centre (NMPCC) is a non-operational arm of the Australian Federal Police (AFP). The NMPCC was established in 2006 to drive national coordination in response to missing persons in Australia, and to complement the investigative role of State and Territory police. Among other services (support services, search agencies, helping with the search, etc.), they provide a range of prevention tools. An example of that is the Australian Police Child ID App, which is a free smartphone application. It is designed to help parents quickly provide personal identification information to police in the event that any of their children go missing.

Availability and Cost: Free, available to public.

Downloads/Links: <https://missingpersons.gov.au>

Potential use in the project: the App was designed and built by AFP based on software provided under licence by the FBI to help parents and guardians more easily collect and send important information about their child/children in the event of a disappearance or abduction. That system could be useful.

27. ECAAS (European Child Alert Automated System)

Operator / Developer: The Smile of the Child

The activation of AMBER/CHILD ALERT in Greece is implemented through ECAAS (European Child Alert Automated System). The picture of the missing child together with personal information (age, name, physical description etc.) are uploaded and the system develops all necessary dissemination material needed (video spot, radio spot, posters etc.). These are sent by email to partners responsible for disseminating the alert and informing the public about the disappearance of the child, including tv and radio stations, newspapers and specific web portals and social media channels.

Availability and Cost: For internal use - activation of AMBER ALERT.

Downloads/Links: <https://www.hamogelo.gr>

Potential use in the project: the ECAAS system standardises and distributes information in multiple means of communication (mobiles, tv, internet, etc.) very quickly.

All the aforementioned systems/software/technologies are tailor made to address specific needs. Due to that fact, and provided that there is no meta-analysis available, one cannot objectively draw conclusion on the strengths and weaknesses of the systems since most of them are incomparable among each other.

2.2.2 Technologies and Systems for Refugee Management

Millions of people are being forced from their homes, risking everything to escape conflict, disaster, poverty or hunger. From those fleeing the war in Syria or climate change-induced droughts, to those stranded in inadequate conditions in Europe, more than 65 million people around the world are now officially displaced from their homes by conflict, violence and persecution – the highest figure recorded by the United Nations since the Second World War.

Given the sheer number of refugees, various systems of data collection and technical capacity constraints, information management on asylum seekers, immigrants and refugees remains one of the biggest challenges.

Technology plays a critical role in the refugee and migrant crisis, through the innovation and provision of tools and solutions to governments, humanitarian organisations and relevant actors in the field, that maintain databases of incoming asylum seekers and migrants.

Moreover, in the current refugee and migrant crisis, the definitions and responsibilities outlined in the UN's 1951 Refugee Convention and subsequent 1967 Protocol are critical principles in guaranteeing to safeguard humanitarian assistance to those most in need. Beyond these agreements, international solidarity and burden-sharing together with collaboration, communication and information dissemination are absolutely necessary for increasing coordination and clarity around the growing migratory issues the world is facing.

Information on asylum seekers often is inadequate to piece together a cohesive picture at the time of decision making. Furthermore, technical standards and platforms are not always consistent across organisations, within and across countries and most databases cannot easily communicate with other databases in different countries.

Addressing challenges in information collection, management and sharing requires collaboration as well as immense technological capacity that can process and match information across billions of queries in a timely, secure and efficient manner. Mobile phone apps can also be used to provide solutions to issues faced by refugees, such as information sharing, housing, safety, aid and fund raising, healthcare, integration and jobs matching.

The three main IT systems in EUROPE regarding data collection, storage and management on immigrants, refugees, asylum seekers and unaccompanied minors are the following:

1. **Eurodac:** centralised EU database that collects and processes the digitalised fingerprints of asylum seekers
2. **Schengen Information System (SIS II):** the largest information system for public security and law enforcement cooperation in Europe
3. **Visa Information System (VIS):** a system that allows Schengen states to share visa data for those who visit or move throughout the Schengen area.

Red Cross/Red Crescent information tools available regarding data collection, storage and management on immigrants, refugees, asylum seekers and unaccompanied minors are the following:

a) Open Data Kit

Open Data Kit (ODK) is a free mobile data collection tool, designed by the University of Washington in 2009, which helps humanitarian organisations, amongst others, to collect, manage and store different kinds of data in Android devices and replace paper-based forms. The huge challenges encountered in the last decades were a critical point which forced the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies to find alternative and innovative systems to approach humanitarian action.

The Monitoring Information System 2.0 was designed by the Spanish Red Cross and implemented during the Greece Population Movement Intervention, in collaboration with the Hellenic Red Cross and other Movement Partners. The system allows the online collection of the data generated as a result of the Red Cross activities. The data are collected through an Android open source application

called Open Data Kit (ODK), storing and managing the mentioned data in a server and sharing the managed results through visual online user-friendly interfaces hosted in the same server.

The data collection is designed to register on real time not only the visits/consultations (and its characteristics) performed in each Red Cross clinic by all the staff in every specialty, but also to count and identify patients. This system allows the medical staff to closely follow up on each patient treated by the Red Cross Health Services (and check the previous tests, prescriptions, symptoms, etc. –i.e. the whole medical file). The hardware used for this aim are tablets specifically configured for the occasion.

All data collected is stored and checked to resolve any possible human mistakes made during the collection process. All found mistakes are shared with the staff in the field to be properly corrected. A strong data protection and security system is in place.

In order to report and share the information collected, the Health Information System 2.0 uses two different online Dashboards particularly designed with Pentaho Business Analytics software for the specific way data is collected. The Health Report Dashboard shows statistical information about the general situation in sites for a specific period; both date and site can be used as filters to access to the desired information for reporting, monitoring or evaluation purposes. The second dashboard, Patients Follow Up, is designed only for the professional use of the medical staff to access to the specific information of the medical record of each patient.

Strengths

- Quick collection of data
- User friendly
- Quick access to statistical analysis

Challenges-Weaknesses

- Necessary to obtain appropriate IT equipment
- Dedicated staff to support its operation

b) Accompanied referrals project (ACCREF)

During the intervention in the Population Movement Crisis in Greece, the Spanish Red Cross has designed several tools in order to build a complete system focused on the collection, storing, management and reporting of the data resulting from the implementation of the activities initially projected.

Red Cross through ACCREF project, offers a team of skilled Interpreters and Cultural mediators (available languages: Arabic, Farsi, Kurmanji, Turkish (Turkey), Urdu, English and Pashtu) accompanying beneficiaries to have access in public services in the urban area of Athens and in Thessaloniki.

Each accompaniment is requested through an urban blog managed by SpRC and the HRC and registered in a digital template during the activity; data collected includes the sector related to requested service (Health emergency, Health Services, AMKA requisition, PSS, social welfare services, advocacy and protection). The registration is done by the cultural mediator/interpreter in charge of the accompaniment using the ODK data collection application.

Strengths

- Easy to use
- Overview of the requested and provided services

c) Virtual Volunteer (Virtualvolunteer.org)

Virtual Volunteer is an easy-to-use Red Cross and Red Crescent web application that provides migrants with the information they need to know, locating services to support them where needed, and connecting them with advice and news that can help them stay safe and healthy.

The application is available from any connected device. **Virtual Volunteer** digitally complements the services offered by the Hellenic Red Cross (HRC) Hotline. The platform provides information and a space to submit questions on topics not addressed in the FAQs. Information can be updated in real-time and reflect changes in trends. The platform can also support hotline operators with an integrated database function for services and more. Given the widespread use of smartphones by migrants in Greece, Virtual Volunteer represents an opportunity to equip large numbers of people with information in an efficient and cost-effective way.

Virtual Volunteer is also a tool for staff and volunteers working on the ground. It offers a space to find updated information, facilitating face-to-face interaction and engagement with migrants.

Though fewer in number, there are still many people on the move in Greece, arriving by sea or land, and Virtual Volunteer is for them a tool to quickly access vital, sometimes life-saving information.

Challenges

The need for human resources to support the update of the information provided.

d) Feedback Database

The Feedback Database was designed in order to track effectively the feedback received from the migrant population in the camps where Red Cross operated (Skaramangas, Ritsona).

The FD was designed in excel form and included useful information regarding: The site, the date, the name of the person who received the feedback, the gender, the language, the type, the channel of the feedback reception, the sector of intervention the feedback was referring, scope and details of the feedback, grade of priority/sensitivity, organization/person to whom the feedback was reported, the date, the channel and details of the action taken regarding the feedback, date of completion and feedback management status.

More particularly, the FD was addressed to the field officers who were communicating and engaging with the migrant community daily, through face-to-face interaction, suggestion boxes, focus group discussions and community meetings.

Strengths

The tool was prepared together with the field officer and was targeting in capturing every potential feedback that needed urgent reply. Also, the staff had the opportunity to follow in detail, the whole procedure of the feedback, before the feedback loop was finally closed. In addition to the above, it was easy to "read" the information regarding the feedback (e.g. type of feedback for the period March to April 2016), due to the automatic statistical representations (very useful also, for the donor's reporting).

Challenges

The fill up of the FD was proven to be very time-consuming, and since the field officers didn't have the time to deal with it, it was slowly abandoned.

2.3 Conclusions & Key Take-aways

In this chapter, a landscape analysis of the main identified domains of interest and relevant technologies has been performed. The landscape analysis has identified that there is significant maturity in the fields of business process reengineering and change management, crowdsourcing, social innovation and collective awareness, but there is limited research on behavioural and activity profiling methodologies that have been modelled to a degree that would allow them to be directly implemented on software platforms.

Regarding Business Process Reengineering and Change Management, the investigation proved that it is feasible to define and introduce the ChildRescue methodology to the NGOs where it will be applied without significantly disturbing their current method of operation, using non-intrusive techniques found in the field of Change Management. The aim will be to introduce some parallel processes to the existing ones that in time will prove to be more effective and efficient and thus drive inter-organisational change without any intrusive involvement of ChildRescue in the process. For this to work, the new processes have to be carefully designed to minimise the effort required to apply them, and to not conflict with neither the stakeholders, processes and legislation.

Furthermore, the extensive research on crowdsourcing, social innovation and collective awareness methodologies and platforms proves that careful design of the platform, the application and the engagement mechanisms for the public at large are crucial for ensuring the success of the project.

Regarding behavioural and activity profiling theories and research, a classification of the most relevant algorithm and theory to use depending on the category that each case belongs to, can help to both prioritise the several pieces of collected data, as well as to provide a mechanism to quantify the relevant ones for feeding the predictive algorithms.

Finally, the review of the state-of-the-art of existing and already applied information systems has shown that during the design of the platform's architecture, several avenues regarding some well-documented good practices and design patterns can be explored, to facilitate the design, the development and the uptake of the platform by the pilot partners.

3 ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for the Missing Children Investigation Cycle

3.1 Stakeholders' Mapping

The purpose of this section is to go one step further from the Stakeholder Identification reported in the context of D1.1 "User Requirements" in section 2.1 and visualise relationships among the different stakeholders and also their mapping to platform's actor roles.

Mapping stakeholders is a visual exercise and analysis tool that supports a better understanding of the often-complex interactions among stakeholders²⁹. In the context of ChildRescue, the objective of this mapping is to render the connections and categorisation of stakeholders into groups more intuitive with the help of a clear diagram and also to map stakeholders with ChildRescue solution actors in a way that all different ChildRescue stakeholders will be concentrated in specific platform's actors and their connections will stand out.

To achieve this objective, the KUMU tool that is a powerful visualisation platform that enables the user to organise complex information into interactive relationship maps was employed. Therefore, stakeholder mapping was implemented using that tool for the interests of ChildRescue, and it can be found in the following link: <https://kumu.io/epuntua/childrescue#map-qPUyTWPF>

²⁹ https://www.bsr.org/reports/BSR_Stakeholder_Engagement_Stakeholder_Mapping.final.pdf

Figure 3-1 ChildRescue Stakeholders & Actors

Figure 3-1 demonstrates an informative screenshot of the mapping realised. However, for further exploration of the ChildRescue stakeholder relationships and their mapping to platform roles it is advisable to visit the provided link.

3.2 Methodology Definition

D1.1 described in detail the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios for the two use cases (“Missing Children Emergency Use Case” and “Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case”) in a space-time continuum. These scenarios were divided into 4 sub-processes: Preparation and Profiling, Coordination and Collaboration, Action, Archiving. The conclusion was that many times, these sub-processes do not occur sequentially, so the overall proposed workflow will be more modular. In this deliverable, the field of the suggested integrated methodology is no longer treated as 4 separate stages which are only temporally connected one after the other, but they are treated as modules which can occur independently of each other and/or parallel to one another. These modules may have different triggers to start up their processes; some can even start on their own, without having to wait a “signal” from another module in order to start.

Except the scope and the workflow at each stage, a dataflow chapter has been added after the Ethics Advisory Board’s suggestion. These chapters describe the data flow between the actors and the purposes for which the data is exchanged at each stage.

The following sections present the workflows and the dataflows of each phase in the ChildRescue lifecycle. The actors that take place in these workflows and dataflows are derived from the actors that are defined in D1.1 and are listed in the table below (Table 3-1 Actors).

Table 3-1 Actors

Stakeholder group	Description
A. Missing children	Missing children are the target of the investigation mission, although not directly engaged in the ChildRescue solution.
B. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors	This group refers to all migrant children under the age of eighteen "who have been separated from both parents and other relatives and are not being cared for by an adult who, by law or custom, is responsible for doing so." ³⁰
C. Legal Guardians and caretakers (Parents, Facility Managers etc.)	In this category, all people who have the legal authority (and the corresponding duty) to care for the personal and property interests of a minor (missing child or unaccompanied minor in the ChildRescue case) are considered. The members of this group are the ones responsible for the initiation of an investigation process, informing the authorities about their missing child.
D. Missing Children Response Organisations	In this group, all organisations that are occupied with the support of the investigation process of a missing child are considered. In Europe, this accounts for all members of the MCE Network, among which, SoC and CF.
E. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors Care Organisations	All organisations that are dealing with the unaccompanied migrant children and their registration and care are part of this stakeholder group. RC represents this group in ChildRescue.
F. Other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations	Any other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations that do not fall into D and E categories, but they are offering, along with other actions and initiatives, their services in the investigation and identification of missing children are concentrated in this group. Any Search and Rescue Teams that do not belong in the Missing Children Investigation Organisations

³⁰ <http://www.unhcr.org/40f646444.pdf>

		themselves (or E. category) are part of this group too.
G.	Governmental Organisations	Apart from the aforementioned organisations, there are also specific governmental agencies/organisations, such as specific ministries, that are responsible for handling such missing children cases. All such governmental agencies fall in this stakeholder category.
H.	Public prosecutors	The prosecutor is the chief legal representative of the prosecution in countries with either the common law adversarial system, or the civil law inquisitorial system ³¹ . Public prosecutors are discriminated from "G" stakeholder group since they play an essential role in missing children cases and especially the decision to issue an Amber Alert. Therefore, they are considered a separate stakeholder group that in many cases represents the government.
I.	Other governmental or private collaborators	Any governmental, public or private organisations or individuals that could be of any help in the investigation of a missing child or an unaccompanied migrant minor (e.g. the fire department, security agencies, bus drivers, etc.) will be contacted and engaged in the investigation process.
J.	Police/ Coast Guard	The police (or the Coast Guard in the case of a missing child near the sea) is the one responsible for searching for a missing child. ChildRescue-enabled insights are aspired to be used directly by the police to guide their investigation towards new, knowledge-based directions.
K.	Citizens – Open, General public	The General Public is a core stakeholder for ChildRescue since ChildRescue aims to engage an as wide as possible audience to participate actively in the discovery of a missing child through the valuable information that citizens close to the place a child was lost may offer.

³¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prosecutor>

For each phase the relevant workflow and dataflow are provided. The workflow is represented in BPMN³² and the dataflow in level 1 Gane and Sarson notation. Each workflow is accompanied with a mapping table where each process that is included into the workflows is described in more detail. We define as **Scenario 1** the “Missing Children Emergency Use Case (to-be scenario)” and as **Scenario 2** the “Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors (to-be scenario)” as they are defined in D1.1.

3.2.1 Preparation and Profiling

3.2.1.1 *Scope*

The main purpose of this phase is the construction of a multilayer profile of the missing person. It includes the personal profile (dictated by the testimonials of the family and friends, the close environment of the missing person), the psychological profile (representing the professional assessment of the social workers and psychologists), and the social profile (analysing the missing person’s presence, activity and traces in social networks). Moreover, the possible POIs of the person are defined using predictive analytics techniques as well as pattern matching with past similar cases.

The main data that are collected, processed and shared during this phase are personal data of the missing person, data concerning his/her psychological and social behaviour, data from public information provided in social networks, as well as open data (geographical and transportation).

3.2.1.2 *Workflow*

The workflow that is followed during the Preparation and Profiling phase includes the main steps that are followed by the ChildRescue methodology and cover both use cases that are described in D1.1. The workflow is presented in Figure 3-2.

The workflow starts with a distinction between the missing child case and the unaccompanied minor case. In the first case, the case responsible acquires information about the missing person as soon as a consent form is signed by the interviewee or a court order has been issued. In the second case the case responsible acquires information as soon as a placement order or tracing request has received. The case responsible checks if the case already exists. If not, a new case is created. The case is further processed from the case responsible by collecting more information from the responsible authorities: police (missing child) or previous hosting facilities (unaccompanied minor). Then case responsible collects information from the family (missing child, tracing service) or the guardian of the child (missing child, tracing service) or from the unaccompanied minor (unaccompanied minor). As soon as the case is stored into the ChildRescue platform, a number of procedures are taking place such as mining of public information from social media, predictive analytics for possible points of interest and past cases pattern matching in order to enrich the case file.

Table 3-2 Preparation and profiling workflow steps

³² Business Process Model Notation v2.0, <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/2.0/>

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity -relevant Actors)	Derived from scenario
01	Request a signed consent form/ Wait for a court or placement order: Groups D and E request from group C to sign a consent form in order to receive the permission to collect and process personal data of the missing child/UM and of group C. The family/guardian signs a consent form to declare that he/she is aware and that personal data will be collected and provide permission for their process	D, E, C	Scenario 1
02	Wait for placement order or tracing request: Group E waits for a placement order to be issued from group G or a tracing request to be made from group C	E, C, G	Scenario 2
03	Send an email and documents to the responsible organization running the hosting facility: Group G sends an email and the relevant documents to the responsible agency of group E	G, E	Scenario 2
04	Acquire personal information about the missing child or the UM: The responsible person (Manager, Coordinator) from groups D, E collects information about the missing child/ Unaccompanied Minor	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
05	Search for a relevant case in the ChildRescue Platform: The responsible person (Manager, Coordinator) from groups D, E searches if there is already a case open for the specific missing child	D, E	Scenario 2

	or an Unaccompanied Minor. In the case of the Unaccompanied Minor a case may be already registered by a previous hosting facility or other organization of group E		
06	Open a new case: If there is no previous record a new case is created by the responsible personnel of groups D, E	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
07	The new case file is stored into the ChildRescue platform: A new case file with the profiling information is created.	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
08	Collect information from authorities (police)/previous hosting facilities: The responsible personnel collects additional information for the missing child/ Unaccompanied Minor from the police (group J) or previous hosting facilities (group E)	D, E, J	Scenario 1
09	Collects information from family/guardian or the unaccompanied minor: The responsible personnel collects additional information from family/guardian (group C). In the case of the unaccompanied minor, group E collects further information from the minor concerning his/her social history, his/her psychological background, his/her intention to leave the current hosting facility etc. by interviewing the minor. In the case of a tracing request the responsible case manager collects information from the person (family member or guardian) that made the tracing request.	D, E, C, B	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
10	Mining of public information from social media: The	D, E	Scenario 1

	responsible personnel collects public information from social media and updates the profile of the missing child/ Unaccompanied Minor		
11	Predictive analytics for possible points of interest: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to enrich the profile	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1
12	Past cases pattern matching: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to identify possible POIs of the missing child/ Unaccompanied Minor	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

Figure 3-2 Preparation and Profiling workflow

3.2.1.3 *Dataflow*

The relevant data flow diagram of the aforementioned workflow is provided below. The main data set that is exchanged between the case responsible and the ChildRescue platform is the case data. As soon as the case data are stored into the platform a set of datastores are created and updated including the multilayer profile of the missing person/unaccompanied minor, data related to information deriving from the social media, predictive analytics for the possible POIs or destinations of the missing person/unaccompanied minor, past cases and data related to pattern matching with past cases.

Figure 3-3 Preparation and Profiling dataflow

3.2.2 Coordination and Collaboration

3.2.2.1 *Scope*

From police and MCOs to volunteer teams, the Samaritan corps and individual citizens, a variety of organisations and entities are engaged in a missing child's investigation operation. Consultation and efficient coordination among parts with such different involvement, jurisdiction and procedures could be a real struggle.

In order to aid the Coordination and Collaboration Stage, ChildRescue will provide a Collaboration Space for each search group, enabling real-time sharing of information and communication among team members, through a group chat as well as through direct messaging. The Collaboration Space will also feature a real-time interactive map showing the location of volunteers and team members, allowing for better operation monitoring and guidance.

The Collaboration Spaces will help teams speed up their procedures (such as building up a team quickly), enhance intercommunication and enable team coordinators to provide guidance and support, while the Case and the other involved Managers will have a complete picture of the investigation progress and updates. They will also serve as communication and collaboration points with organisations abroad when the case extends beyond borders. This can be extremely useful in cases of unaccompanied minors who have crossed a country's borders in order to reach their target destination country, where their relatives may be.

Direct messaging will be available not only for organisation staff members, volunteers and rescuers, but also for simple users and visitors who have uploaded evidence and should be further inquired by the Managers involved in the case. The ability to individually contact anyone having, possibly important, information is crucial for the operations.

The information acquired during the Action phase, after its evaluation and validation, will be diffused to the appropriate receivers through the Collaboration Space management. The same goes for the results of the data analytics procedures that could direct the investigation to new locations and areas. Hosting facilities or the Authorities could also benefit from this component, using it as a means of cooperation and profile sharing, in order to enable easier and fastest recognition of relocated unaccompanied minors.

3.2.2.2 *Workflow*

The Coordination and Collaboration workflow (Figure 3-4) is designed according to the use cases and the requirements derived thereof, as presented in D1.1. It is a unified flow, suitable both for the unaccompanied minor and the missing child scenario. The core of this phase is the provision of a communication tool that will enhance teams during a search mission.

The workflow illustrates the following procedure: When handling an unaccompanied minor case, first comes the distinction between having or not a tracing request. In a case without tracing request, the relevant Facility Managers and other people involved are notified on the status updates through ChildRescue (e.g. appearance of the minor in a new facility, return to facility within one day etc.). In a tracing or a missing child case, a collaboration space is created by the case responsible through the platform. Afterwards, the cooperating S&R team and volunteer group members are notified about the

case and asked for their participation. Whoever confirms availability, joins the collaboration space, otherwise continues as simple user for this case. If any indications that involvement of another country is needed, the case file is shared with the relevant organisation of this country. The organisation is also asked to assist the operations and join the collaboration space. The collaboration space offers a number of functionalities: direct messaging, an interactive map with real-time location of participating team members and secure discussion channels for communication. Through the collaboration space, the responsible personnel communicate directly with individual users or even with whole teams and monitor the team dispersion in the search areas. They also receive other evidence and findings and combined with the estimations of the prediction engine, they can proceed with management of the search mission and guide the teams operating on the field, in alignment with directions from the authorities.

Table 3-3 Coordination and Collaboration workflow steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity -relevant Actors)	Derived from scenario
01	Set up collaboration space for the case: The responsible personnel of groups D, E will create a collaboration space dedicated to this case, which will serve as a communication point for those participating in the search mission	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
02	Update hosting facility managers and other relevant users on case status through ChildRescue: In case of a voluntary departure of unaccompanied minor from a hosting facility without tracing request, the relevant personnel are informed through the platform on any updates	E, F	Scenario 2
03	Send notifications to S&R members, volunteers through ChildRescue: Team members and volunteers are informed on the case and asked of their availability through the platform	D, E, F	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
04	Continue as simple user: If a team member/volunteer cannot participate in the search mission,	K	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

	she/he will continue as a simple user for this case		
05	Share case file with organisation of another country through ChildRescue: If cross-border cooperation is needed, the case file is shared with the relevant organisation of the other country, which is also invited to the collaboration space	D, E, F	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
06	Join collaboration space: All available S&R team members/volunteers can enter the case collaboration space	D, E, F	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
07	Send/receive personal messages to/from specific users: The responsible personnel of groups D, E can send direct messages to individual users who acquire important information or to team leaders for better coordination. The receivers can answer back to these messages	D, E, F, K	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
08	Share real-time location on interactive map: An interactive map will contain the real-time locations of all team members/volunteers participating in the S&R mission	D, E, F	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
09	Communicate events in a secure discussion channel: Individual teams can have their own separate discussion channels for better inter-communication	D, E, F	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
10	Monitor operations and resources: Through the interactive map, the responsible personnel of groups D, E has an oversight of the mission's progress location-wise	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

11	<p>Receive evidence on case through ChildRescue or other means: The ChildRescue case file will be updated with evidences and important information that arise from simple users, S&R team members/volunteers, but also from other sources outside ChildRescue</p>	D, E, F, K	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
12	<p>Data analytics for predicting possible POIs and routes: The ChildRescue prediction engine will estimate possible areas of interest</p>	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
13	<p>Manage collaboration space. Send directions/data to S&R and Volunteer teams: The responsible personnel of groups D, E has a clear overview of the investigation progress and manages the S&R teams/volunteer groups through the collaboration space</p>	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
14	<p>Communication and guidance from Police and external collaborators: The responsible personnel of groups D, E is in close communication with the police and other involved parties</p>	D, E, F, H, I, J	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

Figure 3-4 Coordination and Collaboration workflow

3.2.2.3 Dataflow

Following is the dataflow diagram deriving from the Coordination and Cooperation workflow. Focusing on the main functionality of this phase, we omitted all data pertaining access and login credentials. Policies regarding these data will be discussed in the context of WP3.

For the purposes of collaboration and communication, except for case data (from the child electronic record) and prediction data, there is also exchange of member account data, direct messages (between stakeholders) and text/voice data (from the Discussion Channel). All data is managed centrally through the Data Management component. The involved stakeholders are the responsible personnel of groups D, E, F, the participating rescuers/volunteers, simple users and the authorities. The Collaboration Space receives data from member accounts. The stakeholders can request/provide case data (depending on their entitlement) and exchange direct messages.

Figure 3-5 Coordination and Collaboration dataflow

3.2.3 Action

3.2.3.1 Scope

The current state of the Action Stage, as part of the whole investigation process followed after report of a missing child or a tracing request for an unaccompanied minor, is presented in detail in D1.1. It includes the dissemination of the child's disappearance through a Publicity or Amber Alert Action and activation/coordination of a Search & Rescue mission if requested by the police, or mobilization of the Samaritan corps in case of a natural disaster/ tracing operation.

ChildRescue contributes to the Action Stage by providing a social awareness promoting tool and enabling the active involvement of citizens and volunteers in the missing children investigations. At the same time, it facilitates not only cooperation among members of the Search & Rescue/Volunteer Teams but also cross-team and cross-border coordination and consultation, thus allowing for more effective human resources dispersion in the investigation areas. It should be mentioned that the Coordination/Collaboration and the Action Stage workflows may run in parallel and share activities or affect one another.

The mobile application will be the main conductor towards creating a social awareness network and harnessing the power of collective intelligence. When dissemination of the case is considered appropriate, location-based alerts will be diffused to users of the ChildRescue application, containing all information needed regarding the missing child. The users will not only become aware of the case, but will also be encouraged to actively contribute by sharing possible evidence and information through the application. As the investigation progresses, the alert notifications will be further diffused to new areas of interest.

Evidence and indications uploaded from all ChildRescue users will be automatically evaluated, initially based on the user's profile and history and afterwards on the actual lead they have provided. Crowd validation will also be activated on demand for individual pieces of information.

The predictive analytics algorithms will calculate possible routes and points of interest throughout the whole investigation process, based on new evidence and incoming clues. These suggestions will provide a lead for the spatial orientation of the operations and help raising social awareness in key locations.

3.2.3.2 *Workflow*

For both use cases, the Action stage is activated when investigation for a child is needed, be it a voluntary departure from a hosting facility, a report of a missing child or a disaster affecting unaccompanied minors. The ChildRescue platform will operate in parallel to the actual investigation, adding value to the mission by estimating possible POIs and providing a means of information sharing and dissemination. All these functionalities constitute the Action workflow presented below in Figure 3-6, which includes steps deriving from the scenarios and use cases of deliverable D1.1.

The Action workflow will be followed every time new evidence on the case is provided from a ChildRescue user through the platform. The evidence is registered in the blockchain and is available to the case responsible, who has an oversight of the overall case progress and user input. As volunteers and rescuers play a significant role in the action field, the case responsible can notify them about important findings and give updated directions to the teams through the case collaboration space. The shared information is evaluated before it is used as input to the Prediction Engine. The evaluation is operated from the ChildRescue platform and takes into account different factors, such as the user's history and credibility and the information's accuracy. Under certain circumstances, the contribution of other users may also be needed in addition to the automatic evaluation. If so, this piece of information is sent to users for crowd-validation and the results are also registered to the platform. When the information is finally assessed, the data is used in the dynamic estimation of possible routes and POIs of the child. Based on these predictions, the case responsible can decide on notifying ChildRescue users located in the newly indicated areas by sending alerts with all appropriate information.

Table 3-4 Action workflow steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity Actors)	Derived -relevant scenario	from
01	Commit to ChildRescue blockchain ledger: Evidence from ChildRescue users is registered in blockchain for added trust and verifiability	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
02	Update collaboration space: The responsible personnel of groups D, E will provide directives to S&R/Volunteer teams and may invite more participants based on new findings on the action field	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
03	Send/receive data: The ChildRescue platform will support both incoming and outgoing data from and towards users but also among its own Components	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
04	Real-time management of investigation progress: Overall monitoring of the progress and new findings in the action field and decision-making regarding dissemination to new areas of interest is practiced by the responsible personnel of groups D, E	D, E	Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
05	Evaluate shared information: Credibility of all information and uploaded evidence will be evaluated depending both on the user (e.g. role, contribution history) and the information	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,

	itself (e.g. proximity to POIs etc.)		
06	Request crowd-validation: When deemed necessary, users will be sent evidence in order to confirm it	K	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
07	Route estimation: Possible routes and POIs will be generated from the prediction engine, based on the child's electronic record and on new evidence	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
08	Prepare location-based alerts with information for ChildRescue users: Alerts containing all appropriate information on the child case will be prepared and sent to users located near estimated routes or POIs. Both the data that will be disseminated and the shape and radius of the area will be decided by the responsible personnel of groups D, E	D, E, F, K	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

Figure 3-6 Action workflow

3.2.3.3 Dataflow

All data exchanges resulting from the steps taken throughout the Action workflow are presented in the following Figure 3-7. The involved stakeholders are the responsible personnel of groups D, E, who will monitor all information but also provide case data, and the simple users who will mainly upload information but may also be requested for crowd-validation. Data stores used in the Action phase include the Evidence record (storing of submitted evidence), the Blockchain ledger (adding to evidence trust and validity), the data analytics results (providing suggestions on possible POIs and routes) and the simple users member accounts (for location-based alerts, evidence evaluation). All data is managed through a central Data Management Component.

Figure 3-7 Action dataflow

3.2.4 Archiving

3.2.4.1 Scope

The scope of the Archiving phase is to support the responsible authorities to handle the case's closure in a secure and a privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation of the documentation and lessons learnt of the case is provided internally in order to support its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future. In the case of the mobile application, all data related to the specific case are erased from the citizens' devices, leaving behind only the non-personal information, statistics and outcome of the specific case. The main data that are processed during this phase are the case data including the profiling of the missing child or the unaccompanied minor and the data deriving from the coordination and action phase as they are described in the previous sections.

3.2.4.2 Workflow

The workflow that is followed during the Archiving phase includes the main steps that are followed by the ChildRescue methodology and cover both use cases that are described in D1.1. The workflow is presented in Figure 3-8.

The workflow begins as soon as the case is considered resolved. In the case of the missing child, a case is resolved when the child has been found. In the case of the unaccompanied minor a case is resolved if one the following is taking place: a) the minor has returned to the hosting facility, b) the minor has reached his/her final destination or/and c) the minor reaches a guardian d) the minor reached adulthood while in the care of the relevant organization. For the Tracing Department, a sought person's case is resolved when a) they are traced, or b) 3 years have been reached after the initial tracing request, or c) when the tracing request is cancelled.

As soon as a case is considered resolved (or cancelled) the responsible personnel updates the case with the latest information and closes the case. As soon as a case is closed a number of actions are taking place in parallel: a) the semantic annotation of the case with keywords, metadata and other criteria in order to facilitate the retrieval of the case if required in the future, b) the extraction of analytics and statistics based other similar cases, c) anonymization of the case data in order to remove any personal information and d) encryption of the case data to ensure data security, protection and controlled access. In case the case has already been shared with the citizens to the ChildRescue application during the action phase, the personal data are removed from the case while providing only statistical information related to the case.

Table 3-5 Archiving workflow steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder (Activity Actors)	group -relevant	Derived scenario	from
01	Keep the case open: The responsible personnel of groups D, E keeps the case open until the missing child is found or the Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility	D, E		Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
02	The case is updated: The responsible personnel of groups D, E updates the case that the missing child is found or the Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility	D, E		Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,
03	The case is closed: The responsible personnel of groups D, E closes the case since the missing child is found or the	D, E		Scenario 1, Scenario 2	1,

	Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility		
04	Semantic annotation: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to enrich the case with related information (keywords, categories etc.) in order to facilitate its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
05	Aggregation of past cases: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform to provide a tool for lessons learnt and enhance past knowledge	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
06	Anonymization: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform for data protection and security	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
07	Encryption: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform for data protection and security	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
08	Analytics and statistics generation: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to provide a tool for lessons learnt to the end users	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
09	Deletion of case data from mobile devices: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform for data protection and security	ChildRescue platform	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

Figure 3-8 Archiving workflow

3.2.4.3 Dataflow

The relevant data flow diagram of the aforementioned workflow is provided below. The main data that are exchanged are case data and related data generated from a number of archiving procedures. These data include semantic annotations, analytics and statistics, anonymized and encrypted case data. The main data stores that are used during this dataflow are the case data records, the past cases records and the mobile data records.

Figure 3-9 Archiving dataflow

3.3 Plan for the Adoption of the Methodology: Social Sensors Critical Mass

Having defined in the previous section of Chapter 3, section 3.2, the initial version for the ChildRescue methodology, another important aspect is to acknowledge what is the vision for the adoption of the methodology. That question leads to exploitation issues that will be addressed extensively in the context of WP5. However, one aspect related with the plan for the adoption of the methodology, that of the definition of a social sensors critical mass, will be analysed in this deliverable to attempt to define in an as complete manner as possible the criteria that play a role in the success of the ChildRescue solution and possibly come up in a deeper understanding of critical mass as a number.

Before proceeding with such an analysis, it is essential to define what a social sensor is, how a critical mass is defined, and of course what is the relation of these terms with the ChildRescue interests.

The term **social sensor** is directly connected with Social Networks and Web 2.0 and intends to encapsulate all cases where information is generated expressing some situation and fact about users, such as their preferences or scheduled activities, and their social environment [62]. The idea of social sensors is directly linked with ChildRescue, since ChildRescue aims to leverage the crowd/citizens as a source of information about a missing child, either that is her/his potential location, his/her preferences, the places he/she uses to go out, etc. Therefore, the vision of ChildRescue is to engage a broader audience in the missing children investigation cause that will subscribe in the ChildRescue solution and contribute as social sensors to enrich the information gathered for the missing child in question.

On the other hand, the idea of the **critical mass** is being used for a long time in social sciences, although the term is a more recent adoption. The idea was firstly met with the term "Critical density" in the 1970s by a game theorist, Thomas Schelling in his book "Micromotives and Macrobehavior"³³. Critical mass as a concept originated in physics, referring to the "volume of a nuclear product required to sustain a chain reaction in a nuclear explosion"³³. Critical mass in marketing terms, by analogy with physics, is used to define a very different product, users, required to sustain the "chain reaction" of sales. Critical mass, in that respect, encapsulates the idea that there is a specific, minimum number of users for a product in order for that product to be considered successful. When this critical mass is reached it is perceived that the product is self-sustainable and commercially viable, and it is easier to sell more of it than before this critical mass is reached.

Critical mass is frequently used as a term when dealing with collective actions. There is a certain category of products that require other users to interact together for the product to be useful and successful. Social networks belong to this category of products, as they do need a critical mass of users to use them to actually deliver the experiences they promise. This refers to the data needed for social networks to be able to contribute in detecting properties and characteristics referring to people [62]. Such an example is that of Flickr [63], where there are not enough cities in the world with an adequate number of information to make the tourist recommendation tool applicable.

The critical mass issue is something that ChildRescue puts emphasis, on since it recognises that the system the project intends to build for the missing children investigation cause is something that passes

³³ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/how-to-achieve-critical-mass-for-a-product-launch>

by crowd participation and won't be successful without the involvement of a critical mass of citizens. It is something that is often encountered to focus on the development of tools for the efficient extraction of insights from social sensing data, neglecting the social sensors critical mass issue and the range of the potential users' adoption, resulting in systems and technologies that remain unexploitable and are eventually led to extinction.

The success of crowdsourcing lies on achieving the participation of a critical mass of people in the crowdsourcing initiative [64]. Unfortunately, though, even if being aware of that fact, it is neither a straightforward task to achieve that goal nor to define what is that critical mass point and when it has been reached.

There are certain key performance measures or indicators (KPMs or KPIs) that are being used in businesses to indicate whether you are reaching that critical mass point, such as positive cash flow, healthy margins and revenue flows, customer retention, brand engagement, etc. However, ChildRescue as a CAPS project with a very different and "sensitive" vision than that of a typical business for financial gain, plans to approach this issue from an also differentiated viewpoint.

The goal of ChildRescue concerning the work presented in this section is to better approach the critical mass of people, i.e. the number of people/citizens, that should download and be registered to the ChildRescue mobile application per location in order to significantly improve the chances of a lost child being found in this location. The improvement is counted with respect to the non-use of the ChildRescue application for the investigation of a missing child and the employment of the traditional processes of a given area/country.

The main issue with such an approach is that there is little scientific/academic work right now in the field of citizen sensing to build upon that while the current, existing work has diverse application domains [65]. Therefore, being a yet unexplored research domain, the aim of this section is to present some relevant approaches to be leveraged as an initial roadmap to investigate the research potential of such a problem; the identification of social sensors critical mass per location for the ChildRescue application.

So, it needs to be stressed that due to time limitations the intention of this section is to not to go in a deep analysis and conclusion on such critical mass, but instead just to scratch the surface of these big and yet new and unexplored research problem.

As already stated, diverse and limited published studies can be found in the literature around the subject of citizen sensing, that could be used as a stimulus for ChildRescue. Applications in the field of citizen sensing are often referred to as 'crowdsourcing' or 'participatory sensing' applications, because they step upon the power of the masses and are based on the participation of citizens for the success of their systems and goals [66]. Such applications are becoming increasingly prevailing due to the availability and growing adoption rates of location-aware and Internet-enabled mobile devices, leveraging the opportunity to collect high-scale value-added information at low cost. In this context, (Kamel Boulos et al. 2011), have been occupied with Sensor Web and citizen sensing (or else said "human in loop sensing") in the era of the Mobile and Social Web offering a state-of-the-art review of these fields and their roles in application domains such as environmental protection, public health surveillance and crisis awareness, disaster informatics, the trends and challenges faced in these areas. Among the main challenges information overload, "noise", misinformation, bias (i.e. the propagation of the "popular" opinion, without a control on its truthfulness) and trust are being stated. Therefore, the need for validation of the information shared by citizens/users is explicitly highlighted in many research

papers. As far as humans participation roles is concerned, measurement collection, sensor data processing, information sharing, information fusion and analysis, and humans as information sources are the ones that can be found in the literature [67]. The sensor data (pre-)processing by humans showcases the main differentiation of human sensors with hardware sensors and the reasons why citizen/participatory sensing attains an increasing application and interest.

[65] are suggesting a bottom-up model in which citizens develop and use sensors for urban environment monitoring. Another interesting work is that of [68] where a mobile application is built for its users to be used as sensors for sensing public transport incidents, with an application in the public rail network in the Barcelona metropolitan area. Here, the critical mass issue is explicitly stated as successfully achieved, since they conclude that a representative sample of the reality that they want to "sensorise" is reached through publicity campaigns and an explicit stating of the benefits of the application to the own users, while they also highlight as a challenge the fidelity of users and its maintaining.

Another whole application domain of citizen sensing is the so called Wikification of GIS (Geographic Information Systems) by the masses [69] or else said Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) [70], where Google Earth is such a characteristic example. In VGI's validation of the users' contributions and discrimination of the most important ones is also essential and [71] are attempting to solve such a challenge by applying a spatio-temporal segmentation method and specifically three criteria: geospatial criteria, temporal criteria (i.e. creating time intervals, in accordance with the expected characteristics of the event of interest) and event criteria, in the sense that a true event will be documented by more citizens.

Finally, [72] are specifically dealing with the question of how to transform such citizen sensing applications with an initially small-scale application-specific network to a commercially successful application that will be part of people's everyday lives. The aim of this paper is to formulate a general-purpose, large-scale social sensing system to be easily adopted by and applied to a wide variety of applications in urban settings (e.g., enterprises, hospitals, recreational areas, towns, cities, and the metropolis). To accomplish that, they are introducing the mobility characteristics of a sensor as a core criterion for the success of the sensing operation and the coverage of a field by a network of mobile sensors as a core issue. Therefore, they develop MetroSense that is based on an opportunistic sensor networking approach, according to which mobility-enabled interactions are leveraged and people-centric mobile sensors, static sensors and edge wireless access nodes are exploited. In this paper, their people-centric mobile sensors network is compared with a static one with respect to the area they cover on each case. While a static network has also a fixed coverage area, a broader sensor coverage is achieved by the network they build. A simulation experiment is also presented for a population of mobile sensors to validate their declarations. The mobility characteristics of a sensor in order for him/her to probabilistically be in the right place at the right time to sense the item of interest is also examined.

To conclude, it is acknowledged that citizen sensing applications have to the following characteristics: to be (a) horizontal, allowing information sharing, (b) semi-structured, not restricting users in very tight and specific formats and templates, in order to give them the freedom to report what they consider relevant and appropriate, (c) real-time, (d) open, (e) geo-aware, in the sense that local citizens testimonies are more likely to be valid, (f) accessible to anyone, in the sense that it should not require the latest technologies in mobile phones to work properly but be able to apply to the simplest mobile phone [66].

As already stated, ChildRescue aims to leverage the state-of-the-art on social sensing in mobile applications, part of which is presented in the context of this deliverable, to pinpoint routes for the identification of social sensors critical mass per area for the ChildRescue interests. In that view, for the months to come, further literature analysis will take place followed by the development of the ChildRescue approach in the critical mass identification problem, considering all the different criteria that play a role in the definition of that number, such as the population density of the area/location in question, the mobility characteristics of the social sensors, etc., and combining them under one model using statistical analysis and decision support methods. If useful conclusions can be drawn from this analysis, its results and the respective model for the ChildRescue social sensors critical mass identification will be reported in the update of this deliverable, i.e. D1.4 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release II" on M21.

4 Conclusions & Next Steps

In this deliverable the focus has been to consistently and analytically describe the methodology by which ChildRescue will be applied and implemented as a software platform. The main domains of interest have been identified, as have the current technologies used in the fields of the investigation of missing children and the management of refugee flows and individuals. Moreover, the stakeholders related to the ChildRescue processes have been identified, linked, and presented using advanced visualisation techniques. The identified workflows from the TO-BE scenarios have been merged and designed to combine both pilot cases, into the four-step process of the investigation cycle. With those, the relevant data flows have been identified and mapped. Finally, a piece of innovative research into the quantification of the ideal number of mobile users per geographic area and a prioritisation of the mobile application end-user uptake goals has been suggested.

The results from this deliverable will be used to provide a source for various tasks throughout the project which means that it is an enabler of various of its key elements. While moving forward with the tasks of “WP2 - Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation” and “WP3- ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation”, changes to the methodology are expected and will be documented. The same applies with the results from the beginning of the first cycle of the pilot operation. These changes will be integrated to this deliverable together with any new findings stemming from the research, design, development and pilot operation of ChildRescue.

5 Annex I: References

- [1] R. Todnem By, "Organisational change management: A critical review," *J. Chang. Manag.*, 2005.
- [2] J. Jones, D. Aguirre, and M. Calderone, "10 Principles of Change Management," 2004.
- [3] J. W. Moran and B. K. Brightman, "Leading organizational change," *J. Work. Learn.*, 2000.
- [4] J. R. Phillips, "Enhancing the effectiveness of organizational change management," *Hum. Resour. Manage.*, 1983.
- [5] a a Armenakis and a G. Bedeian, "Organizational change: A review of theory and research in the 1990s," *J. Manage.*, 1999.
- [6] A. Mento, R. Jones, and W. Dirndorfer, "A change management process: Grounded in both theory and practice," *J. Chang. Manag.*, 2002.
- [7] M. Zairi, "Business process management: A boundaryless approach to modern competitiveness," *Bus. Process Manag. J.*, 1997.
- [8] P. Trkman, "The critical success factors of business process management," *Int. J. Inf. Manage.*, 2010.
- [9] M. Dumas, M. La Rosa, J. Mendling, and H. A. Reijers, *Fundamentals of Business Process Management*. 2013.
- [10] W. M. P. Van Der Aalst, M. La Rosa, and F. M. Santoro, "Business process management: Don't forget to improve the process!," *Bus. Inf. Syst. Eng.*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 1–6, 2016.
- [11] R. K. L. Ko, "A Computer Scientist's Introductory Guide to Business Process Management (BPM)," *Crossroads XRDS*, 2009.
- [12] J. vom Brocke and M. Rosemann, *Handbook on business process management 1: Introduction, methods, and information systems*. 2015.
- [13] P. O'Neill and A. S. Sohal, "Business process reengineering a review of recent literature," *Technovation*, 1999.
- [14] T. H. Davenport and J. E. Short, "The New Industrial Engineering: Information Technology and Business Process Redesign," *Sloan Manage. Rev.*, 1990.
- [15] M. Hammer and J. Champy, "Reengineering the corporation: A manifesto for business revolution," *Bus. Horiz.*, 1993.
- [16] R. Talwar, "Business re-engineering-a strategy-driven approach," *Long Range Plann.*, 1993.
- [17] D. P. Petrozzo and J. C. Stepper, "Successful Reengineering," *New York Van Nostrand Reinhold*, 1994.
- [18] J. N. Lowental, "Reengineering the organization. A step-by-step approach to corporate revitalization," *Qual. Prog.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 61–63, 1994.
- [19] D. C. Brabham, "Crowdsourcing as a Model for Problem Solving: An Introduction and Cases," *Converg. Int. J. Res. into New Media Technol.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 75–90, 2008.
- [20] E. Estellés-Arolas and F. González-Ladrón-De-Guevara, "Towards an integrated crowdsourcing definition," *J. Inf. Sci.*, 2012.
- [21] T. Buecheler, J. H. Sieg, R. M. Fuchslin, and R. Pfeifer, "Crowdsourcing , Open Innovation and Collective Intelligence in the Scientific Method : A Research Agenda and Operational Framework Why Crowdsourcing in the Scientific Method," *Alife XII Conf. Odense, Denmark*, 2010.
- [22] F. Kleemann, G. G. Voß, and K. Rieder, "Un(der)paid Innovators: The Commercial Utilization of Consumer Work through Crowdsourcing," *Sci. Technol. Innov. Stud.*, 2008.
- [23] J. Howe, "Crowdsourcing: Why the Power of the Crowd Is Driving the Future of Business," Aug. 2008.
- [24] M. Vuković, "Crowdsourcing for enterprises," *Serv. 2009 - 5th 2009 World Congr. Serv.*, no. PART 1, pp. 686–692, 2009.
- [25] V. Chanal, "How to invent a new business model based on crowdsourcing : the Crowdsprit ® case How to invent a new business model based on crowdsourcing : the Crowdsprit ® case," 2008.

- [26] D. Brabham, "Using Crowdsourcing In Government," *IBM Cent. Bus. Gov.*, 2013.
- [27] G. Chatzimilioudis, A. Konstantinidis, C. Laoudias, and D. Zeinalipour-Yazti, "Crowdsourcing with smartphones," *IEEE Internet Comput.*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 36–44, 2012.
- [28] A. Baruch, A. May, and D. Yu, "The motivations, enablers and barriers for voluntary participation in an online crowdsourcing platform," *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 64, pp. 923–931, 2016.
- [29] H. El Alaoui El Abdallaoui, A. El Fazziki, A. Sadiq, E. F. Zohra, and M. Sadgal, "A web based crowdsourcing framework: Lost child case," in *Colloquium in Information Science and Technology, CIST*, 2017, pp. 263–268.
- [30] F. Alt, A. S. Shirazi, A. Schmidt, U. Kramer, and Z. Nawaz, "Location-based crowdsourcing: Extending crowdsourcing to the real world," in *NordiCHI 2010: Extending Boundaries - Proceedings of the 6th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*, 2010, pp. 13–22.
- [31] R. K. Ganti, F. Ye, and H. Lei, "Mobile crowdsensing: Current state and future challenges," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 49, no. 11, pp. 32–39, 2011.
- [32] J. M. Lampinen, J. Arnal, and J. L. Hicks, "The effectiveness of supermarket posters in helping to find missing children," *J. Interpers. Violence*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 406–423, 2009.
- [33] A. Passani, F. Spagnoli, F. Bellini, A. Prampolini, and K. Firus, "Collective awareness platform for sustainability and social innovation (CAPS): Understanding them and analysing their impacts," in *Lecture Notes in Information Systems and Organisation*, 2016, vol. 13, pp. 103–114.
- [34] G. Mulgan, S. Tucker, R. Ali, and B. Sanders, *Social Innovation: What it Is, Why it Matters and How it Can Be Accelerated*. 2007.
- [35] R. Heiskala, *Social innovations: Structural and power perspectives*. 2007.
- [36] J. A. Phills, K. Deiglmeier, and D. T. Miller, "Rediscovering social innovation," *Stanford Soc. Innov. Rev.*, 2008.
- [37] A. Gaggioli, "Digital Social Innovation," *CYBERPSYCHOLOGY, BEHAVIOR, Soc. Netw.*, 2017.
- [38] F. Bria, "Growing a Digital Social Innovation Ecosystem for Europe," *Dsi Final Rep.*, 2015.
- [39] H. Halpin and F. Bria, *Crowdmapping digital social innovation with linked data*, vol. 9088. 2015.
- [40] J. Heinzelman and C. Waters, "Crowdsourcing Crisis Information in Disaster," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2010.
- [41] J. Lawson, Tony and Garrod, *Dictionary of Sociology*. 2001.
- [42] L. M. Camarinha-Matos, J. Goes, L. Gomes, and J. Martins, *Towards Collective Awareness Systems*, vol. 423. 2014.
- [43] M. Daassi and M. Favier, "Groupware and Team Aware," in *Encyclopedia of Virtual Communities and Technologies*, 2006.
- [44] I. Lykourantzou, D. J. Vergados, E. Kapetanios, and V. Loumos, "Collective intelligence systems: Classification and modeling," *J. Emerg. Technol. Web Intell.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 217–226, 2011.
- [45] J. Surowiecki, "The Wisdom of Crowds," *How Collect. Wisdom Shapes Bus. Econ. Soc. Nations New York Doubleday*, 2004.
- [46] G. Pacini and F. Bagnoli, *Results of a collective awareness platforms investigation*, vol. 9934 LNCS. 2016.
- [47] L. Jacovella and P. Lio, "Speeding up the transition to collective awareness," in *2013 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops, ICC 2013*, 2013, pp. 220–224.
- [48] H. Shin *et al.*, "CoSMiC: Designing a mobile crowd-sourced collaborative application to find a missing child in situ," in *MobileHCI 2014 - Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services*, 2014, pp. 389–398.
- [49] K. S. Greene, "The more eyes the better? A preliminary examination of the usefulness of child alert systems in the Netherlands, United Kingdom (UK), Czech Republic and Poland," 2016.
- [50] E. Frith, "Social media and children's mental health: a review of the evidence," 2017.
- [51] S. D. Young, "Behavioral insights on big data: Using social media for predicting biomedical outcomes," *Trends Microbiol.*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 601–602, 2014.
- [52] S. Anisuzzaman, Anissa., and Y. Morimoto, "Finding Key Persons on Social Media by Using

- MapReduce Skyline," *Int. J. Netw. Comput.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 86–104, 2017.
- [53] L. White, K. Burger, and M. Yearworth, "Understanding behaviour in problem structuring methods interventions with activity theory," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 249, no. 3, pp. 983–1004, 2016.
- [54] R. H. Burke, "An Introduction to Criminological Theory," *Fa Yi Xue Za Zhi*, 2014.
- [55] S. P. Borgatti, A. Mehra, D. J. Brass, and G. Labianca, "Network analysis in the social sciences," *Science*. 2009.
- [56] M. Er, "Activity Theory," in *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Action Research*, Los Angeles, Calif, 2014.
- [57] J. O. Beasley *et al.*, "Patterns of prior offending by child abductors: A comparison of fatal and non-fatal outcomes," *Int. J. Law Psychiatry*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 273–280, 2009.
- [58] J. I. Warren *et al.*, "An investigative analysis of 463 incidents of single-victim child abductions identified through Federal Law Enforcement," *Aggression and Violent Behavior*. 2016.
- [59] A. Rutherford *et al.*, "Targeted Social Mobilization in a Global Manhunt," *PLoS One*, 2013.
- [60] U. Schäffer Jürgen Weber Utz Schäffer Jürgen Weber Liebe Leserinnen, "Controlling & Management Review Big Data Big Data – Big Chance für Controller?," *Control. Manag.*, 2016.
- [61] A. Cancedda, L. Day, D. Dimitrova, and M. Gosset, "Missing Children in the European Union. Mapping, data collection and statistics," 2013.
- [62] A. Rosi, M. Mamei, F. Zambonelli, S. Dobson, G. Stevenson, and J. Ye, "Social sensors and pervasive services: Approaches and perspectives," *2011 IEEE Int. Conf. Pervasive Comput. Commun. Work. PERCOM Work. 2011*, pp. 525–530, 2011.
- [63] M. Mamei, A. Rosi, and F. Zambonelli, "Automatic Analysis of Geotagged Photos for Intelligent Tourist Services," in *2010 Sixth International Conference on Intelligent Environments*, 2010, pp. 146–151.
- [64] O. Alonso, D. E. Rose, and B. Stewart, "Crowdsourcing for relevance evaluation," *ACM SIGIR Forum*, vol. 42, no. 2, p. 9, Nov. 2008.
- [65] Q. Jiang *et al.*, "Citizen Sensing for Improved Urban Environmental Monitoring," *J. Sensors*, vol. 2016, pp. 1–9, May 2016.
- [66] M. N. Kamel Boulos *et al.*, "Crowdsourcing, citizen sensing and sensor web technologies for public and environmental health surveillance and crisis management: Trends, OGC standards and application examples," *Int. J. Health Geogr.*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 67, 2011.
- [67] M. Srivastava, T. Abdelzaher, and B. Szymanski, "Human-centric sensing," *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 370, no. 1958, pp. 176–197, Jan. 2012.
- [68] C. Tanas and J. Herrera-Joancomartí, "Users as Smart Sensors: A Mobile Platform for Sensing Public Transport Incidents," Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 81–93.
- [69] M. Boulos, "Web GIS in practice III: creating a simple interactive map of England's Strategic Health Authorities using Google Maps API, Google Earth KML, and MSN Virtual Earth Map Control.," *Int. J. Health Geogr.*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 22, Sep. 2005.
- [70] M. F. Goodchild, "Citizens as sensors: the world of volunteered geography," *GeoJournal*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 211–221, Nov. 2007.
- [71] S. Schade *et al.*, "Citizen-based sensing of crisis events: Sensor web enablement for volunteered geographic information," *Appl. Geomatics*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 3–18, 2013.
- [72] A. T. Campbell, S. B. Eisenman, N. D. Lane, E. Miluzzo, and R. A. Peterson, "People-centric urban sensing," in *Proceedings of the 2nd annual international workshop on Wireless internet - WICON '06*, 2006, p. 18–es.